

Synthesis of assessment findings in the form of two discussion papers (evolving into scientific articles and policy briefs)

MATS Deliverable 3.7

MATS

making agricultural trade sustainable

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Preface

“Modern societies have acquired an amount of economic wealth, scientific knowledge, and technological capacities that should enable to fund and implement most of the transformations that The Limits to Growth saw as paramount in terms of creating a sustainable world. ... The time has come, we believe, for a new Enlightenment or for otherwise overturning current habits of thought and action that only consider the short term.

The Executive Committee of the Club of Rome”

(Preface to: Von Weizsäcker, E. U., & Wijkman, A. (2017). *Come on!: capitalism, short-termism, population and the destruction of the planet*. Springer.)

“Trade is a good thing and occurs only if both sides expect benefits from it. But trade is also a segment of international competition, which can lead to the defeat of weaker companies or entire states, and trade has enormous effects on natural resources and the environment in general but so far lacks appropriate rules protecting those public goods. The world will need a new appreciation of balance ...”

(Von Weizsäcker, E. U., & Wijkman, A. (2017). *Come on!: capitalism, short-termism, population and the destruction of the planet*. Springer, p. 38)

Below, the reader will find two inter-connected discussion papers. In Discussion paper 1 (DP1), we present thirty-one leverage points, i.e. key points of intervention, that have the potential to contribute to more sustainable agricultural trade, arising from investigations of those actors, regions and commodities which were part of the MATS case studies. The subsequent DP2 aims to set the foundations to link MATS empirical case study evidence with theoretical notions of leverage points, levers and reinforcing feedback in a systems-context, to explain how key points of interventions that

make use of reinforcing feedback can support transformative changes toward more sustainable agricultural trade.

Nearly half of the thirty-one leverage points identified and discussed below in DP1 relate to policies, governance, and regulations; nine pertain to economic and market elements; six to social capital; and one to human capital, specifically knowledge and skills. The first discussion paper DP1 concentrates on leverage points within each contextual dimension of the agricultural trade system as they were assessed through the MATS case studies and in the context of previous literature. We provide information on potential actions for change and case study-specific conditions supporting actions for change

In the subsequent discussion paper DP2, we focus only on those intervention points that we identify as strategic cross-cutting in their potential to transform the agricultural trade system. These are those leverage points recognized each in more than 5 of the 15 MATS case studies and located in at least two of the four SDG regions investigated under MATS [(1) Sub-Saharan Africa, (2) Northern Africa and Southern Asia, (3) Northern America and Europe, (4) Latin America and the Caribbean].

We consider our MATS findings presented in DP1 and DP2 as offering actionable information on leverage points and intertwined levers that could feed into the pathways to sustainability identified in the IPBES Global Assessment. Considering the focus of DP2 on strategic cross-cutting leverage points, we hope that it not only simplifies the challenges facing policymakers in looking for entry-points and prioritization; we also hope that we have contributed with a conceptually-based multi-actor application of the interplay of enabling conditions, reinforcing feedbacks and interventions to trigger systemic changes that could be applied to other research projects with multi-actor settings beyond MATS.

Finally, we hope that both discussion papers contribute to a better practical and conceptual understanding of the relevance of the diversity of contextual conditions in agri-food systems when policymakers aim to identify key points of intervention on which to design more sustainable agricultural trade interventions and policies.

Levers and leverage points for achieving more sustainable agricultural trade: Insights from MATS case studies synthesis

MATS Deliverable 3.7 – Discussion paper (1)

This project receives funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme under Grant Agreement No 101000751.

Summary

It is well established that collaborative implementation of priority interventions (levers) targeting key points of intervention (leverage points) can potentially enable transformative changes from current trends towards more sustainable ones (Chau et al., 2020). If global agri-food systems actors are interested in making agricultural trade more sustainable, along multiple sustainability dimensions, a collaborative implementation of levers targeting effective leverage points is therefore of central importance. Yet, when we consider the diversity of commodities, regions, and actors' perspectives in agricultural trade worldwide, as reflected in the 15 MATS case studies, it is a priori unclear what such a collaborative implementation could entail in a complex multi-actor setting such as that of MATS. The objective of this discussion paper – which is based on underlying synthesis evidence from case studies summary work D3.5. – is to provide actionable evidence, a sense of potential prioritization and clarity on the key leverage points that may contribute to more sustainable agricultural trade in the context of those actors, regions and commodities which were investigated as part of the MATS case studies. The attempt is to provide policy-relevant insights on actionable implementation of levers of change by value chain actors and policymakers toward more sustainable agricultural trade. To that end, we provide information on (i.) potential actions for change and (ii.) case study-specific conditions supporting actions for change. Since previous MATS work has established a five-dimensional framework to explore the complexity of agricultural trade systems from a sustainability lens, the subsequent focus on levers and leverage points relates to these five dimensions. The five dimensions (namely “policy, governance, and regulations”, “social capital”, “human capital”, “natural capital”, and “economy and markets”) allow illustrating the contextual diversity of MATS 15 case studies, which address diverse commodities, regions, and actors from the agricultural trade system.

We provide evidence on thirty-one leverage points below, where attempts are made to identify them in terms of their leverage potential also through color

code (red, orange, yellow – see Tables in the Appendix), following realms of leverage (Abson et al., 2017) reflecting a gradient from shallow leverage points to deep leverage points (Fischer et al., 2019). These priority points for intervention (Chan et al., 2020) have arisen directly from the MATS case study work and are, therefore, a direct reflection of the regional, commodity, and SDG coverage under MATS, hence differ from the Food System Summit 2021 levers in how they were derived, yet corroborate substantively with the Food System Summit 2021 focus on human rights, innovation, finance, gender equality, and women’s empowerment. In particular, the strong social sustainability (human rights) focus of the MATS case studies reinforces the importance of the Food System Summit 2021 levers identified. Furthermore, relative to the broader IPBES Global Assessment, where one of the components of the assessment applied a social-ecological systems lens in the identification of the most important elements of pathways to sustainability (Chau et al., 2020), we have identified a more fine-grained landscape of leverage points and intertwined levers, acknowledging the commodity, regional and actor-diversity of the 15 MATS case studies. In this way, our MATS findings could be seen as offering detailed actionable information on leverage points and intertwined levers that could feed into the pathways to sustainability identified in the IPBES Global Assessment.

Nearly half of the thirty-one leverage points identified and discussed below relate to *policies, governance, and regulations*; nine pertain to *economic and market elements*; six to *social capital*; and one to *human capital*, specifically knowledge and skills. This discussion paper concentrates on leverage points within each contextual dimension of the agricultural trade system as they were assessed through the MATS case studies and in the context of previous literature. Each section offers insights on two levels. At the first level, we illustrate the strategic interventions proposed by the MATS case studies through the leverage points identified within the agricultural trade system, to advance the Sustainable Development Goals. These interventions are built upon a set of ideas for action shared by the MATS 15 case studies, each focusing on one or more agri-food commodities located in different regions and countries. At the second level, we offer insights on case-study specific conditions supporting actions for change, by providing a break-down of the

interventions proposed by MATS case studies while summarizing the context-specificities that explained their call for such actions. This level of analysis aims to delve into the nuances and specificities of the strategic actions, thus providing policymakers and value chain actors with insights for their implementation across diverse agri-food systems worldwide.

Our MATS case studies identify environmental sustainability and investments as well as social sustainability dimensions of key importance for the desired systems change. Considering the social sustainability dimensions and human rights violations found under MATS, it is noteworthy that in focusing on strategic interventions in the social dimension to transform agricultural trade, we show below how acting on six social leverage points identified in MATS could trigger systemic changes in agricultural trade that promises to support their positive impacts on several SDGs identified. The case studies recognizing the strategic role of collaboration, integration, and synergy among actors call for equitable, fair, and empowering approaches that strengthen the agency of stakeholders (mostly small-scale farmers) who are frequently marginalized from decision-making processes.

In guiding our reader through the five dimension of the agricultural trade system (“policy, governance and regulation”; “social capital”; human capital”; “natural capital”, and “economy and markets”) and the corresponding leverage points discussion, our goal is to make this a tangible exercise, so that value chain actors and policymakers alike could take actionable lessons from it. Let us start the journey.

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“Transformative change towards sustainable pathways requires more than a simple scaling-up of sustainability initiatives—it entails addressing these levers and leverage points to change the fabric of legal, political, economic and other social systems.”

(Chan et al., 2020: 694)

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1. Introduction

This discussion paper is guided by a systems perspective and is the result of the synthesis of the 15 MATS case study analyses and associated completed tasks¹. The overarching idea is threefold while focusing on leverage points for change; first, to enable cross-case comparability in terms of analysis steps, methods, and results; second, to ensure robustness of the derived results and recommendations; and third, to enable transferable lessons across commodity, geographic and other domains while retaining a meaningful level of fine-grained case-based insights.

Our focus on leverage points for change is implemented by providing information on (i.) potential actions for change and (ii.) case study-specific conditions supporting actions for change. By capitalizing on the identified levers of change, the objective is to discuss how agricultural trade may actively contribute to achieving selected Sustainable Development Goals.

The previously completed CS Summary Report (D3.5) serves as basis for this discussion paper. In preparation for D3.5., the case studies were examined individually to provide contextualized evidence of the linkages between agri-food value chain activities and the broader political, social, human, natural,

¹ Within task T3.3, we implemented follow-up meetings and briefing sessions with CS teams to support them during implementation and reporting. For this purpose, we also used the data pool and insights from the normalizing work in D3.4 Common data pool on sustainability standards and competitiveness. The CS common reporting template and a CS Guidance Table for the Adoption of the Systems Approach were the main guidance documents shared at the beginning of the process. These were shared while highlighting the relevance of D3.1. and D3.4. for the purpose of comparability and consistency among CS in following implementation steps (fieldwork, analysis) and reporting. Thereby, by distinguishing these documents with guiding instructions, we obtained individual CS contributions and joint CS contributions to WP3, thereby serving the overall MATS systemic ambitions.

and economic context, and to identify leverage points and strategic actions with the potential to accelerate transformation processes toward sustainability. Based on the leverage points and levers of change arising directly from the case study evidence (D3.5.), this discussion paper provides complementary insights to the transition pathways analysis (D5.2), which used MATS-internal consortium members and selected external actors as part of a foresight process based on four webinars and one workshop in World Café style to derive those transition pathways. The complementary insights arising from this discussion paper focus on (i.) case-study based potential actions for change and (ii.) case study-specific conditions supporting actions for change. Taken together, the insights from this discussion paper (D3.7, DP1), the complementary discussion paper DP2, and the forthcoming foresight process report (D5.2.) aim to provide actionable evidence for global value chain actors and policymakers on leverage points and transition pathways toward more sustainable agricultural trade.

2. Leverage points and strategic interventions toward more sustainable agricultural trade

The MATS case studies analyses are providing insights into the linkages between global, national, and regional agri-food value chain activities, including the broader political, social, human, economic, and environmental contexts. This exploration of linkages was based on a multi-methods approach, aiming to connect micro- and macro-perspectives on the underlying reasons (drivers) for un-sustainable trade. In particular, our approach was focusing on the sustainability impacts of trade policies, and the relationships of trade policies with specific sustainability dimensions (and SDGs). The analyses have revealed leverage points within the agricultural trade system that can enhance its positive impacts on sustainability while mitigating negative effects. In the following sections, we synthesize and discuss the leverage points emerging from the summary work D3.5. In doing so, we follow influential work on human–environment systems by Donella Meadows and subsequent work (Fischer et al., 2019), who has identified leverage points as places in a system where relatively minor interventions can lead to relatively major changes in certain outcomes (Meadows, 1999; Meadows, Meadows, Randers, & Behrens, 1972). Meadows (1999) and subsequent work identified a hierarchy of leverage points, where the underlying factors of this hierarchy relate to *both* causal relationships thinking as well as to teleological and thus purpose-thinking. Causal relationship thinking is related to normative endpoints (Fischer et al., 2019), which we consider here in MATS, in our analysis built upon D3.5., reflected in strategic interventions and corresponding SDGs (see Figure 1, below) that reflect decided and thus normative endpoints. As Fischer et al.

(2019) highlight, this engagement with future desired endpoints is also a reflection of backcasting thinking (Dreborg, 1996), where the means to reach these desired points are determined in response.

The nature and advantages of a leverage points perspective relate thus to the very multi-methods approach in MATS, since our macro-level modeling (incl. Gravity modeling, Computable General Equilibrium Modeling), meso-level (incl. System Dynamics modeling at the level of value chains), and micro-level modeling approaches (micro-econometric analyses of farmer, consumer and other value chain actor surveys) build on causality and predictive modeling assumptions. Hence, taken together, our MATS multi-methods approach embracing a causal relationship thinking, and the subsequent leverage points analysis both capture causality and teleology through multiple approaches, thereby providing a solid foundation for the leverage points prioritization in this discussion paper DP1 and for DP2.²

A total of thirty-one leverage points is identified and discussed below, where attempts are made to identify them in terms of their leverage potential also through color code, following realms of leverage (Abson et al., 2017) reflecting a gradient from shallow leverage points to deep leverage points (Fischer et al., 2019). These key points of intervention (Chan et al., 2020) have arisen directly from the MATS case study work and are, therefore, a direct reflection of the regional, commodity, and SDG coverage under MATS, hence differ from

² For the origins of teleology and its relationship to the concept of causation, see van Glasersfeld (1990). Fischer et al. (2019: 117) highlight that "Causal relationships of course still exist when operating in backcasting mode, but causality is drawn on within firmly defined bounds of teleology – that is, 'the explanation of phenomena in terms of the purpose they serve rather than of the cause by which they arise' (Oxford Dictionaries, 2018). Backcasting thus allows for the creative pursuit of truly bold goals that will routinely fall outside the bounds of what forecasts based on current systems understanding predict."

the Food System Summit 2021 levers³ in how they were derived, yet corroborate substantively with the Food System Summit 2021 focus on human rights, innovation, finance, gender equality, and women's empowerment. In particular, the strong social sustainability (human rights) focus of the MATS case studies reinforces the importance of the Food System Summit 2021 levers identified. Furthermore, relative to the broader IPBES Global Assessment, where one of the components of the assessment applied a social-ecological systems lens in the identification of the most important elements of pathways to sustainability (Chau et al., 2020), we provide a more fine-grained landscape of leverage points and intertwined levers, thanks to the commodity, regional and actor-diversity of the 15 MATS case studies.

Nearly half of these leverage points identified here relate to (2.1.) policies, governance, and regulations; nine pertain to (2.2.) economic and market variables; six to social structures and conditions (2.3.); and one to human variables (2.4), specifically knowledge and skills. Although no leverage points were directly identified within the environmental dimensions, it is crucial to acknowledge their critical role in transforming the agricultural trade system.

The following sections summarize and discuss the identified leverage points within each contextual dimension of the agricultural trade system and in the

³ "A lever of change can be understood as an area of work that has the potential to deliver wide-ranging positive change beyond its immediate focus." (<https://www.un.org/en/food-systems-summit/levers-of-change>). Collaborative implementation of priority interventions (levers) targeting key points of intervention (leverage points) can potentially enable transformative changes from current trends towards more sustainable ones (Chau et al., 2020).

context of previous literature. Each section offers insights on two levels, as illustrated by Figure 1.

- *First level:*

We illustrate the strategic interventions proposed by the MATS case studies through the *leverage points* identified within the agricultural trade system. These interventions are built upon a set of ideas for action shared by the MATS 15 case studies, each focusing on one or more agri-food commodities located in different regions and countries around the world. To illustrate the origins of the strategic actions, we indicate the locations and agri-food commodities in the case studies underpinning each action. We also illustrate how the strategic actions proposed contribute to a more sustainable agricultural trade by advancing the Sustainable Development Goals. To achieve this, we matched the results of each of the specific conditions and actions for change in each case study using an SDG Text Mining tool (<https://www.scanner2030.com/>) against the SDGs identified in the CS Guidance Table for the adoption of the systems approach.

- *Second level:*

We provide a detailed break-down of the interventions proposed by MATS case studies while summarizing the *context-specificities* that explained their call for such actions. This level of analysis aims to delve into the nuances and specificities of the strategic actions, thus providing policymakers and value chain actors with valuable insights for their implementation across diverse agri-food systems worldwide.

FIGURE 1. ANALYTICAL FRAMEWORK

2.1. Policy, governance, and regulations

The MATS case studies identified fifteen leverage points within the policy and governance dimension that promote a more sustainable agricultural trade. These strategic points for action encompass governance structures, power imbalances, and various policies, regulations, and standards.

Given the transformative potential of the leverage points, our MATS case studies synthesis work prioritizes upon them through 30 strategic actions to make the agricultural trade potentially more sustainable.

In the following section 2.1.1, we summarize those actions as suggestions for informed and adaptable decision-making. In addition, we link the strategic actions to the Sustainable Development Goals, thus illustrating their contributions to the transformation of the agricultural trade.

Next, in section 2.1.2, we provide a more detailed break-down of the interventions proposed by MATS case studies while summarizing the context-specificities that explained their call for such actions.

Throughout this discussion paper, we follow this same structure of discussion as in 2.1.1. and 2.1.2. for all sustainability dimensions (“policy, governance and regulation”; “social and human dimensions”, “economy and markets”).

2.1.1. Strategic interventions in policy and governance to transform agricultural trade - Insights to inform policy-making

Figure 2 illustrates how acting on the 15 policy and governance-related leverage points identified would trigger systemic changes in the agricultural trade that maximize their positive impacts on certain Sustainable Development Goals.

From the 15 leverage points listed in Figure 2, we highlight those receiving more support from across regions and agrifood products investigated. We highlight the intervention points recognized as strategic in more than five of the 16 agri-food commodities analyzed in MATS countries located in at least two different SDG regions.

- *Governance structures and mechanisms (PG2)* are recognized as strategic intervention points to achieve a more sustainable agricultural trade system. This is supported by case studies working on eight agrifood products in ten different countries across Sub-Saharan Africa, South America, and Europe. These MATS case studies highlight the need for accountability, due diligence, and justice mechanisms in governance and political structures that contemplate the social and environmental dimensions of trade besides the economic one.

As shown in Figure 2, acting on governance structures and mechanisms would impact on at least eight Sustainable Development Goals, according to MATS findings: SDG 3 Good Health and Wellbeing, SDG 6 Clean Water and Sanitation, SDG8 Decent Work and Economic Growth, SDG9 Industry, Innovation, and Infrastructure, SDG10 Reduced Inequalities, SDG11 Sustainable Cities and Communities, SDG15 Life on Land, and SDG17 Partnerships for the Goals.

Previous work highlights also the role of *governance structures* at organizational levels in the context of cooperatives (Candemir et al., 2021; Teixeira et al., 2020), as we found evidence in the context of cooperatives in Africa (coffee, Tanzania) that supporting such governance structures is key for balanced value chain relationships and improved market access.

- *Food policies (PG9)* are recognized as strategic intervention points by case studies working on nine agri-food products in seven MATS countries across Sub-Saharan Africa and North Africa. These MATS case studies highlight the need to nuance food policies to smallholder farmers' needs. In that sense, they call for enhancing agricultural sovereignty by introducing local products in national food security strategies, supporting farmers technically and financially to be more sustainable and competitive, and instilling price premiums for those to act more sustainable and produce higher quality products.

As shown in Figure 2, enforcing and designing better food policies would impact on at least eight Sustainable Development Goals, according to MATS findings: SDG 2 Zero Hunger, SDG 6 Clean Water and Sanitation, SDG7 Affordable and Clean Energy, SDG8 Decent Work and Economic Growth, SDG9 Industry, Innovation, and Infrastructure, SDG10 Reduced Inequalities, SDG11 Sustainable Cities and Communities, and SDG12 Responsible Consumption and Production.

Previous literature has provided widespread evidence on the key role of nuanced food policies in their respective geographical and institutional context to smallholder farmers' needs (Jayne et al., 2010; Singh et al., 2016).

- *Labor policies and legislations (PG10)* are recognized as leverage points by MATS case studies working on seven agri-food products in 16 countries across Sub-Saharan Africa, North Africa, North America and Europe, and South America. These MATS case studies highlight the need to enforce labor policies that protect farmers and workers' rights and prohibit

child labor, fostering a more sustainable and equitable future for children and local communities.

As shown in Figure 2, enforcing and designing labor policies and legislations would impact on at least seven Sustainable Development Goals, according to MATS findings: SDG1 No Poverty, SDG 2 Zero Hunger, SDG 5 Gender Equality, SDG8 Decent Work and Economic Growth, SDG10 Reduced Inequalities, SDG11 Sustainable Cities and Communities, and SDG12 Responsible Consumption and Production.

Previous works reinforces our findings regarding the need to enforce labor policies that protect farmers and workers' rights and prohibit child labor (LeBaron, 2021; Odijie, 2020), also highlighting the inter-linkages between leverage points spanning investments and workers' rights (Gyapong, 2020). Yet our MATS case evidence (avocado, mango: Kenya) also brings forward another inter-linkage, namely the perceptions of farmers that the very *process* of certification for production practices helps them to better understand labor laws, what a better work environment means, and the process fosters their ability to subsequently comply more effectively with the standards.

In conclusion, it is essential to intervene in PG2 Governance structures and mechanisms, PG9 Food policies, and PG10 Labor policies and legislation, within the *Political, governance, and regulations* dimension of the agri-food system – to make agricultural trade more sustainable worldwide. While recognizing these three as strategic points for action across commodities, actors, and regions, the design of interventions must be nuanced according to context.

FIGURE 2. STRATEGIC INTERVENTIONS IN POLICY AND GOVERNANCE TO TRANSFORM AGRICULTURAL TRADE – INSIGHTS FOR POLICYMAKING.

2.1.2. Policy, governance, and regulatory leverage points, and potential actions for transforming the Agricultural Trade System

The Table 2 (Appendix) goes into further detail, to make a given leverage point actionable. To do so, each leverage point is first specified by potential actions for change, and then it is made transparent from which commodity and regional case-study context these actions arise from ("*CS-specific conditions supporting actions for change*"). The idea is that once a reader has identified her interest in specific "Insights or strategic interventions to inform policymaking" (2.1.1) – here regarding policy, governance, and regulation – then the Table 2 (Appendix) provides further detail for policymakers and local value chain actors on the proposed actions. For example, when considering PG2, governance structures, and mechanisms, the potential action under the corresponding proposed PG2.1. *Enhance governance structures* relates to the establishment of initiatives such as the coffee industry stabilization fund, a coffee research institute, free coffee seedling production and distribution, and the promotion of cooperative institutions.

As for the leverage points identified under this dimension, each has one or more proposed actions aimed at transforming the agricultural trade system investigated. For instance, there is a single proposed action on environmental regulations, water, and energy policies, while four actions target governance structures and mechanisms, and five focus on food policies.

Each action is identified as strategic by one or more case studies in MATS. To illustrate the level of support within MATS, we use a *color code* in Table 1 and the following tables.

TABLE 1. RELEVANCE LEVEL WITHIN MATS

Color code	Description
Red	5 or more MATS case studies identify the action as relevant/ necessary.
Orange	2 to 4 MATS case studies identify the action as relevant/ necessary.
Yellow	The action is proposed by one MATS case study, responding to specific conditions that are not shared with the rest of the case studies.

To focus the dialogue and discussions with previous literature on the most relevant actions for change, we highlight below those actions related to the three main leverage points identified in section 2.1.1. (PG2, PG9, and PG10), which are also supported by two or more MATS case studies.

- **PG 2.1. Enhance governance structures to change the dynamics of agrifood systems and contribute to sustainable development:** Supported by two case studies in four Sub-Saharan African countries, this action illustrates the importance of strong governance structures for the sustainability of agri-food systems in this region. These case studies emphasize the importance of public-private partnerships and initiatives that work cohesively and comprehensively to support sustainable agri-food systems. Coffee industry stabilization funds, coffee research institutes, and free seedling production and distribution are examples offered by a MATS case study in Tanzania (CS1b) that illustrate how to strengthen governance structures in food systems.

- **PG 2.2. Enhance due diligence and accountability mechanisms to account for socio-economic and environmental risks and impacts:** Supported by three case studies in two Sub-Saharan African countries and two Latin American countries, this action emphasizes the importance of incorporating risk assessments, due diligence, transparency, accountability, and remediation mechanisms in policies and regulations. These elements will ensure that projects and regulations account for socio-economic and environmental risks and impacts under the lens of human rights.
- **PG 9.4. Support policies that promote sustainable agricultural practices:** Supported by three case studies in two Sub-Saharan African countries and one Northern African country, this action emphasizes the importance of sustainable agricultural practices to enhance the competitiveness, equity, and resilience of the agri-food sector.
- **PG 9.5. Enhance financial and technical support for farmers:** Supported by two case studies in Uganda and Ghana, this action calls for assisting farmers technically and financially in adopting sustainable and cost-efficient practices to comply with the requirements to access formal markets and to be more competitive.
- **PG 10.1. Enforce labor regulations to comply with safety standards and protect workers' rights:** Supported by five case studies in thirteen countries across Sub-Saharan Africa, Northern Africa, Latin America and the Caribbean, and Northern America and Europe, this action calls for enforcing regulations that comply with safety standards and support workers' rights, through the inclusion of social services, in-

insurance, guaranteed medical care, fair compensations, and more equitable pay structures. Nuancing retirement age policies safeguarding the sustainability of these systems is also considered a critical action to enforce labor rights in food systems.

2.2. Human dimension

The MATS case studies identified a single lever within the human dimension for promoting sustainable agricultural trade: knowledge and skills.

2.2.1. Strategic interventions in the human dimension to transform agricultural trade - Insights to inform policymaking

Figure 3 illustrates how improving farmers' knowledge and skills would trigger systemic changes in the agricultural trade that maximize their positive impacts on certain Sustainable Development Goals, particularly in reducing poverty (SDG1), moving toward zero hunger (SDG2), promoting decent work and economic growth (SDG8), reducing social inequalities (SDG10), developing sustainable cities and communities (SDG11), and fostering responsible consumption and production (SDG12).

Farmers' knowledge and skills are recognized as strategic points of intervention by MATS case studies working on five agrifood products in four different countries across Sub-Saharan Africa and North Africa. These case studies highlight the necessity of empowering especially small-scale farmers through enhanced technical, economic, financial, and marketing knowledge and skills, to strengthen their position and agency in food systems while contributing to sustainability.

Previous literature corroborates with our findings regarding the need for small-scale empowerment and knowledge transfer, not only in other sectors (e.g. fish: Hasan et al., 2020; March et al., 2022) but also with regard to a re-occurring theme in the MATS case studies, that of a knowledge and empowerment bias against women in agri-food value chains (Benitez et al., 2020), as exemplified in the lack of access to credits for women in African value chain in MATS case studies.

FIGURE 3. STRATEGIC INTERVENTIONS IN THE HUMAN DIMENSION TO TRANSFORM AGRICULTURAL TRADE – INSIGHTS FOR POLICYMAKING.

2.2.2. *Leverage points and potential actions within the human dimension for transforming the Agricultural Trade System*

Table 3 (Appendix) goes into further detail to make farmers' knowledge and skills actionable. To do so, this leverage point is specified by potential actions for change, and then it is made transparent from which commodity and regional case-study context the actions arise from.

We briefly present below the two actions for change proposed within the human dimension, which are supported by two MATS case studies each.

- **H 1.1. Bolstering farmers' bargaining power and participation in decision-making:** This action is supported by two MATS case studies focused on coffee systems in Tanzania and potato systems in Egypt. Despite their different contexts, both case studies underscore the necessity of empowering farmers through enhanced knowledge. By improving their technical, economic, financial, and marketing skills, farmers can ensure fairer and more transparent deals, strengthening their position in agrifood value chains.

The previous literature on small-scale farmers' bargaining power and inclusiveness regarding decision-making is extensive. Important contributions have been made with respect to the problems and limitations for increasing inclusiveness, in particular due to inclusion biases, trade-offs and scaling dilemmas also related to cross-thematic coordination issues (Schoneveld, 2022; Arthur et al., 2022). The literature has also highlighted the role of increased participation in the context of leveraging public policy to enable food sovereignty (Brent, 2023), reinforcing our MATS findings.

- **H 1.2. Fostering sustainable production practices:** This action is backed by two MATS case studies – avocado and mango systems in Kenya and wine systems in South Africa. These studies both emphasize the need for training programs to promote sustainable farming techniques. The South African wine case study points to broader farmer empowerment from comprehensive training and education programs. The Kenyan case study particularly highlights the interlinkages between the adoption of sustainable production practices (incl. GlobalGAP) and farmers’ bargaining power, as it revealed that farmers which had been certified received greater trust (also into their quality) by avocado and mango traders and banks providing loans to farmers. However, mango and avocado farmers’ perceptions are that certification for sustainable production practices does not provide greater access to local or international markets, as micro econometric analysis suggests.

In contrast to our evidence that sustainable production practice adoption does not necessarily increase foreign market access through increased trust and access to capital, previous literature on sustainable production practices adoption has concentrated on identifying the (lack of) farmer income contribution of being certified, especially in the case of GlobalGAP (Chiputwa et al., 2015; Ruben et al., 2011; Ruben et al., 2012; Astrid Fenger et al., 2017; Holzapfel et al., 2014; Annor et al., 2023).

2.3. Social dimension

The MATS case studies identified six leverage points within the social dimension of change to promote a more sustainable agricultural trade. These strategic points for action include collaboration and synergy among stakeholders, R&D, knowledge dynamics and capacity building, gender equality, and land tenure (introduced in Section 2.3.1, Figure 4).

Given the transformative potential of the leverage points, MATS case studies prioritize acting upon them through nine strategic actions to make the agricultural trade more sustainable (Section 2.3.2, Table 4).

2.3.1. Strategic interventions in the social dimension to transform agricultural trade – Insights for policy making.

Figure 4 illustrates how acting on the six social leverage points identified in MATS case studies could trigger systemic changes in the agricultural trade that maximize their positive impacts on certain Sustainable Development Goals.

From the six leverage points listed in Figure 4, we highlight *S1 Collaboration, integration, and synergy among stakeholders* as recognized in 11 of the 16 agri-food commodities analyzed in MATS, in countries located in more than two SDG regions – Sub-Saharan Africa, Northern Africa & Western Asia, Latin America and the Caribbean, and Europe & Northern America.

The case studies recognizing the strategic role of *Collaboration, integration, and synergy among actors (S1)* call for equitable, fair, and empowering approaches, including strategic alliances, that strengthen the agency of stakeholders who usually are marginalized from decision-making processes. By adopting these approaches, we hope to advance the Sustainable Development Goals. In particular, on poverty reduction (SDG 1), zero hunger

(SDG 2), gender equality (SDG 5), decent work and economic growth (SDG 8), industry, innovation and infrastructure (SDG 9), reducing inequalities (SDG 10), responsible consumption and production (SDG 12) and partnerships for the goals (SDG 17).

Previous literature focusing on the leverage points of strategic alliances and agency of stakeholders in agri-food value chains has highlighted strategic alliances in the context of multi-stakeholder platforms (MSPs), highlighting the issue of scaling in limiting the effectiveness of MSPs as agents of agri-food system transformation (Thorpe et al., 2022). Our case evidence seems to support this finding, as for example evidence from the Tanzania coffee sector suggests that scaling-up cooperatives remains a key issue. Furthermore, this literature has also highlighted the role of farmer capabilities for successfully engaging in new strategic alliance relationships, with regard to prior alliance relationships experience and farm resource heterogeneity (Steiner et al., 2017). Also, in regard to pricing models that support collaboration, integration, and synergy, negotiated transfer pricing has been investigated, concluding that the issue of transfer pricing in global agri-food value chains likely has important implications for farmer agency due to its connection to fairness and trust when multinationals set prices (Steiner, 2007).

FIGURE 4. STRATEGIC INTERVENTIONS IN THE SOCIAL DIMENSION TO TRANSFORM AGRICULTURAL TRADE – INSIGHTS FOR POLICYMAKING

2.3.2. *Leverage points and potential actions within the social dimension for transforming the Agricultural Trade System*

The table 4 (Appendix) goes into further detail, to make a given leverage point actionable. To do so, each leverage point is first specified by potential actions for change, and then it is made transparent from which commodity and regional case-study context these actions arise from.

As for the six leverage points identified under this dimension, each has one or more proposed actions aimed at transforming the agricultural trade system investigated. For instance, there is a single proposed action on gender equality, knowledge dynamics, land tenure, and societal awareness, while three actions target collaboration, integration, and synergy among stakeholders.

Nine potential actions for making agricultural trade sustainable were proposed as interventions on the identified leverage points related to social structures and dynamics (Table 4 - Appendix). To focus the dialogue and discussions with previous literature on the most relevant actions for change, we highlight below those actions related to *Collaboration, integration, and synergy among stakeholders* – highlighted in 2.3.1 – which are also supported by two or more MATS case studies.

- **S 1.1. Integrating stakeholders along the value chain:** Supported by eight case studies across South America, Sub-Saharan Africa, North Africa, and Europe, this action illustrates the widespread relevance of stakeholders' integration for sustainable agricultural trade systems. These studies show that integrating stakeholders empowers farmers, enhances their bargaining power, and promotes equity and fairness. By reducing reliance on dominant players, these case studies show that

coordinated efforts with a shared vision give farmers a competitive advantage. Evidence-based advocacy and involving stakeholders from planning to execution ensure that the needs and livelihoods of marginalized groups are considered, leading to more inclusive and sustainable agricultural systems.

The issue of equity, fairness and stakeholder integration in value chains has received intensive scrutiny in the literature. Swinnen & Maertens (2007: 98) highlight two potential equity issues with value chain processes; the first concerns the distribution of rents in vertically coordinated food supply chains; the second concerns the participation and exclusion of smallholders and poorer farmers in contract farming. We could consider both being relevant in international trade-dependent value chains, as in the case of MATS case studies based in Africa (e.g. coffee, cocoa, olive oil, mango, avocado). If we consider previous evidence on integrating value-chain actors such as small-scale farmers more effectively into the value chain, for reducing reliance on dominant players, it seems the evidence is that lack of trust between farmers and other value chain actors is a re-occurring issue (Steiner, 2007). For example, Kilelu et al. (2017) provide evidence that hub coordination in smallholder dairy farming in Kenya is limited by such trust issues. The study by Kilelu et al. (2017) conceptualizes the hub as a mix between a broker of relationships, a one-stop-shop for services and a cluster of producers and service providers, enabling horizontal coordination (between smallholders) and vertical coordination (between smallholders and value chain actors and service providers). Yet trust tensions emerged in the combination of horizontal and vertical coordination as farmer organizations as hub operators had to balance a role as an

honest broker between farmers with the intent of enhancing collective action, and as a business-oriented entity which resulted in the exclusion of some farmers who cannot deliver the quantity and quality required to minimize coordination costs (Kilelu et al. (2017). Similar to Kilelu et al. (2017) providing evidence from Africa on the importance to take a holistic perspective of all value chain actors, Boix-Fayos et al. (2023) provide an even broader holistic point of view in the context of making EU-based agri-food policies more sustainable through the Green Deal, by arguing that the transformation to sustainable agriculture, as expected from the several revised strategies, is not just a technical question of farming practices, but requires a holistic approach considering social, economic, cultural, technical and environmental aspects (Boix-Fayos et al., 2023). Other work on integrating value-chain actors corroborates the role of trust and trust building, since it suggests that inclusiveness is not a state of being, but mainly a process (Ros-Tonen et al., 2019) as it underlies trust-building in alliances, and that inclusiveness comprises economic, social, relational, and environmental dimensions (Ros-Tonen et al., 2019).

- **S 1.2. Encourage the establishment of alliances/ partnerships between food systems actors:** Supported by three case studies located across Sub-Saharan Africa and Northern Africa, this action illustrates the relevance of strengthening linkages between food systems actors across different value chains – cassava, banana, goats, cocoa, and olive oil - to foster collaboration and collectively address critical issues that particularly smallholder farmers and their families.

If we consider additional evidence on value chain alliances and partnerships from the literature beyond that discussed above, the

literature highlights the difficulty of integrating knowledge generally (Ireland et al., 2002), yet the difficulty with establishing novel alliances in a trade agreement context has been identified in relation to the lack of regulatory sovereignty (Hoekman et al., 2017) as well as the lack of functioning local institutions (unable to enforce voluntary sustainability standards) linking to trade-relevant international institutions (de Cordoba et al., 2018). Relatedly, the issue of establishing successful partnerships as a function of lack of functioning regulatory institutions can also be showcased by the complexity of existing sustainability standards and its consequences (Sukanya et al., 2024), such that there is a need to appreciate the close inter-relationships between public regulations and private standards and the continuing ways in which private standards evolve (Henson et al., 2010). One response to these issues of establishing new partnerships in the context of developed economies has been the idea of fostering instead (instead to, for example, traditional alliances or cooperatives) alternative agri-food networks (Allen et al., 2017; Higgins et al., 2008). Relatedly, values-based food chains have been identified as a particular type of mid-tier supply chain formed through creating alliances between producers and their supply chain partners, to distribute significant volumes of high-quality, differentiated food products while maintaining transparent relationships and fair distribution of revenues (Ostrom et al., 2018). Despite these re-occurring issues of transparency and market power asymmetry (Steiner, 2007), in principle, Ruben (2024) remains more optimistic that 'new value chain alliances' can support structural transformation of market governance.

- **S 1.3. Strengthen associativity of smallholder farmers to improve their participation in decision-making:** Supported by two case studies located in four Sub-Saharan African countries, this action illustrates the importance of associations or cooperatives in this region to improve farmers' knowledge and skills, competitiveness, and participation in markets, living conditions, and agency in decision-making processes.

If we consider previous evidence on supporting cooperatives as a leverage point, previous literature has highlighted the role of cooperatives in terms of their advocacy capacity for individual farmers (Ton et al., 2014), thereby questioning also the adequacy of standard competition policies towards cooperatives (Ménard, 2007). Cafer et al. (2018) have however qualified the role of cooperatives as only one of several factors to support the technology adoption among small-scale farmers.

2.4. Economy and Markets

The MATS case studies identified nine leverage points within the economy and market dimension to promote a more sustainable agricultural trade. These strategic points for action – introduced in Section 2.4.1., Figure 5 – ranges from economy and finance-related instruments and conditions (e.g., taxation, subsidies, investments) to market and trade-related conditions (information access and transparency, trade agreements and policy frameworks, trade tariff measures, market access, and competitiveness).

Fifteen potential actions were proposed as interventions on these leverage points (Section 2.4.2, Table 5).

2.4.1. Strategic interventions in the economy and market dimension to transform agricultural trade – Insights for policy making.

Figure 5 illustrates how acting on the nine economy and market-related leverage points identified in MATS case studies could trigger systemic changes in the agricultural trade that maximize their positive impacts on certain Sustainable Development Goals.

From the nine leverage points listed in Figure 5, we highlight those supported by more than five out of the 16 agri-food commodities analyzed in MATS and in countries located in at least two different SDG regions.

- *Access to credits and funding (EM1)* is recognized as a strategic point of intervention to achieve a more sustainable agricultural trade system by case studies working on six out of 16 agri-food products in six different countries across Sub-Saharan Africa and Northern Africa. These case

studies highlight the need for alternative financing mechanisms designed for smallholder farmers to enhance resilience and productivity.

As shown in Figure 5, improving farmers' access to credits and funding would impact on at least three Sustainable Development Goals, according to MATS findings: SDG8 Decent Work and Economic Growth, SDG10 Reduced Inequalities, and SDG12 Responsible Consumption and Production.

- *Public and private investments (EM3)* are recognized as strategic intervention points to achieve a more sustainable agricultural trade system by case studies working on eight out of 16 agri-food products in six different countries across Sub-Saharan Africa and Northern Africa. These case studies call for investments in modern and environmentally friendly technology and infrastructure to enhance productivity, cost-efficiency, and sustainability.

As shown in Figure 5, promoting responsible public and private investments could impact on at least three Sustainable Development Goals, according to MATS findings: SDG10 Reduced Inequalities, SDG12 Responsible Consumption and Production, and SDG16 Peace, Justice, and Strong Institutions.

- *Trade agreements and policy frameworks (EM6)* are recognized as strategic points of intervention by case studies working on six out of 16 agri-food products in five different countries across Sub-Saharan Africa and Northern Africa. These case studies call for protective policies to shield farmers from the risks of trade liberalization – e.g., volatility of world market prices, fairness and transparency in trade transactions, and food self-sufficiency.

As shown in Figure 5, acting on trade agreements and policy frameworks would impact on at least three Sustainable Development Goals, according to MATS findings: SDG8 Decent Work and Economic Growth, SDG10 Reduced Inequalities, and SDG12 Responsible Consumption and Production.

Although supported only by five out of 16 agri-food commodities, we also highlight *Agricultural subsidies and trade tariff measures (EM4)* as supported by case studies located in all the SDG regions analyzed in MATS – Sub-Saharan Africa, Northern Africa and Western Asia, Latin America and the Caribbean, and Northern America and Europe. These case studies call for enhancing state agricultural subsidies to support small and medium-scale farmers to be more sustainable and competitive. For instance, subsidies that help them ensure farm viability by alleviating audits and standards compliance costs, mitigating the rising costs of essential inputs, or adopting technology that enhances their competitiveness. Concerning trade-tariff measures, MATS case studies call for enforcing import restriction policies to protect local farmers and shield the domestic market from unsustainable EU trade practices, while concerns regarding the viability of the competitiveness of local farmers remain (e.g. for a viable African Continental Free Trade Area (AfCFTA)).

As shown in Figure 5, developing agricultural subsidies and protective trade tariff measures could impact on at least five Sustainable Development Goals, according to MATS findings: SDG8 Decent Work and Economic Growth, SDG10 Reduced Inequalities, SDG12 Responsible Consumption and Production, SDG15 Life on Land, SDG16 Peace, Justice, and Strong Institutions.

In conclusion, we highlight the relevance of these four leverage points and strategies for making the agricultural trade worldwide more sustainable, responding to diverse contexts and issues in different regions and agrifood systems.

If we consider previous work on such leverage points as *access to credits* (EM1) as a key leverage point, the evidence suggests that agri-food businesses and investors need indices and other benchmarking mechanisms to inform decision making on access to credits (Negra et al., 2020), an issue that is pursued further in the developing MATS Sustainable Trade Hub ([STH](#)). Considering *public and private investments* (EM2), previous work suggests that fuzzy regulatory context and stakeholder influence can negatively impact international trade and investment agreements (TIAs) relevant to global agri-food value chains; in particular, Garton et al. (2022) suggest that lack of awareness or understanding of the implication of TIAs on policy space for regulation can contribute to regulatory chill and policy inertia. The role of *trade agreements* (EM6) has been discussed in previous MATS works (D1.3., D4.3.). Yet previous literature has also repeatedly identified the lack of clarity of formulating a country's domestic sustainability standards with accusations of standards being disguised as trade restrictions (Erixon et al., 2020), as more recently exemplified in the CBAM discourse (Carlson et al., 2023). Previous work has also questioned the fundamental ability of trade rules (WTO) in being able to support climate change mitigation toward a more sustainable agricultural sector, as contrary to the official discourse of 'mutual supportiveness' between trade and environment agreements, WTO rules and commitments may prevent climate action, for agriculture generally as well as with specific solutions for the development dimension (Häberli, 2016).

FIGURE 5. STRATEGIC INTERVENTIONS IN THE ECONOMY AND MARKETS DIMENSION TO TRANSFORM AGRICULTURAL TRADE – INSIGHTS FOR POLICYMAKING.

2.4.2. *Leverage points and potential actions within the economy and markets dimension for transforming the Agricultural Trade System*

Table 5 (Appendix) goes into further detail, to make a given leverage point actionable. To do so, each leverage point is first specified by potential actions for change, and then it is made transparent from which commodity and regional case-study context these actions arise from.

As for the nine leverage points identified under this dimension, each has one or more proposed actions aimed at transforming the agricultural trade system investigated. For instance, there is a single proposed action on taxation in the agri-food value chain, competitiveness, market access, public & private investments, and access to credit & funding. On the other hand, three actions target agricultural subsidies & trade tariff measures and voluntary standards.

To focus the dialogue and discussions with previous literature on the most relevant actions for change, we highlight those actions related to the four main leverage points identified in section 2.4.1. (EM1, EM3, EM4, EM6), which are also supported by two or more MATS case studies.

- **EM 1.1. Promote alternative financing mechanisms:** Supported by three case studies located in five Sub-Saharan African countries and one North African country, this action calls for improving the financial support for smallholder farmers through alternative mechanisms or by adapting financial products to better cope with their needs and constraints.

An extensive literature on alternative financing instruments has focused on the provision of micro-credits for small-scale farmers while promoting to rethink traditional microfinance risk focus (Röttger,

2015), also by linking micro-finance to cooperative participation (Akanji, 2018; Hambolu, 2021). Furthermore, the literature has discussed the use and limitations of smartphone-based technology, in particular for transforming the agri-food sector (Musa et al., 2021; Aker et al., 2016), as well as the role of quality measurement and certification technologies more generally (Steiner (2017)).

- **EM 3.1. Promote investments in modern infrastructure and technology:** Supported by four case studies in Northern and Sub-Saharan Africa, this action calls for investments in environmentally friendly technology to create more resilient farming systems and storage facilities to enhance accessibility, reduce transaction costs, and prevent losses. These investments are crucial for improving agricultural productivity and sustainability.

Previous literature focusing on supporting the investment and adoption of environmentally friendly production, processing and transport technologies for the desired sustainability transition has a surprisingly long history in the agri-food context (MacRae et al., 1990). Recent works stress the key role of introducing such technologies in an inclusive way, naturally to prevent a further marginalization of individual value chain actors, such as small-scale farmers (Klerkx, et al. 2020; Deichmann, et al., 2016), corroborating further our MATS findings.

- **EM 4.1. Enhance state agricultural subsidies:** Supported by five case studies located in thirteen countries across Sub-Saharan Africa, Northern Africa, Northern America and Europe, and Latin America and the Caribbean, this action highlights the need for subsidies that facilitate

access to inputs, technologies, and infrastructure to enhance the competitiveness of agrifood products. They also stress the importance of protecting farmers from price volatility, alleviating the costs of compliance with standards and regulations, ensuring farm viability, and fostering equitable resource distribution between large companies and small and medium-scale farmers.

Previous studies exploring farmers' adoption of production practices and insurance mechanisms for improved risk management highlight not only the issue of family labor shortages being relevant for risk management (Bishu et al., 2018), hinting at child labor issues. They also highlight existing informal risk management practices of farmers as key reasons for the lack of insurance adoption (Smith, 2016), and that it is the joint implementation of risk management strategies (alias synergies) that is important for the risk exposure reduction effectiveness, hence incentives should be designed correspondingly (Birthal et al., 2021). Furthermore, there is a needed balance between private and public investments (subsidies) also as a function of available and functioning private institutions (Dorward et al., 2015), while more recent literature clarifies the reason why development finance institutions have tended to disinvest from primary production agriculture companies and to move to agriculture finance and agroindustry (Ducastel et al., 2024).

- **EM 4.3. Enforce import restriction policies and control measures to strengthen domestic production:** Supported by two case studies located in different countries across Sub-Saharan Africa, Northern Africa, Latin America and the Caribbean, Northern America and Europe, this action calls for enforcing import restriction policies for animal-derived products such as dairy products and beef meat to support domestic

products and shield national markets against unsustainable trade practices.

Early works considering the implications of regulatory heterogeneity, here for example with respect to the enforcement of import restriction policies and control measures, suggest that welfare losses can be expected under such heterogeneity (Winchester et al., 2012). Other literature related to import restrictions regarding animal-derived products has focused on instrumental power related to both public financial support and private sector companies (Vallone et al., 2023). More recent work showcases a trade-relevant global geographical relocation of dairy production and processing, partly driven by large multinational companies who are investing in more intensive forms of farming (Bojovic et al., 2023). Hence, this also corroborates with our MATS case studies leverage point on enforcing import restriction policies such that market power asymmetry issues need to be safeguarded between small-scale actors and multinationals.

- **EM 6.1. Strengthen protective policies to shield farmers from volatile world market prices:** Supported by three case studies located in Uganda, Tanzania, and Tunisia, this action calls for adapting policies to mitigate the risks associated with market liberalization and a corporate-led regime that lacks fairness and transparency.

Previous works which have assessed the effectiveness of policies mitigating farmer risks associated with market liberalization have had an extensive focus on the design of policy reforms in ways that promote efficient and stable market development and protect the interests of the poor (Byerlee, et al., 2006). More recent work corroborates our MATS

leverage point identified above, on the role of strengthening protective policies, since it shows that the mere announcement of new trade policies can cause global food price commodity volatility (Brander et al., 2023). Related works have focused on the role of cooperatives to support market access and lower transaction costs. Tuna & Karantininis (2021) advance cooperatives as social capital hubs acknowledging their role for enhancing network-based trust and thus potentially lowering transaction costs, which finds support in our MATS avocado and mango case studies. Yet Shiferaw et al. (2011) identify a series of challenges and associated transaction costs cooperatives face in improving access to markets and technologies for enhancing productivity of smallholder agriculture. More recent work explores what role the agri-food system could play as a source of employment in the future, arguing that future policies – also those applicable to the Global South – need to promote inclusive agricultural chains and social insurance schemes, and ramp up in agricultural education and extension (Christiaensen et al., 2021).

3. Discussion and conclusions

The above identification and examination of thirty-one leverage points emerged from MATS case studies summary work. Through a systemic analysis of MATS case studies, we illustrate the interlinkages between agri-food value chain activities and five contextual dimensions - namely "policy, governance and regulation"; "social capital"; "human capital"; and "economy and markets" - under a sustainability perspective. We implemented our leverage points analysis above by providing information on (i.) potential actions for change and (ii.) case study-specific conditions supporting actions for change. By capitalizing on the identified levers of change, our objective was twofold. First, the objective was to show how agricultural trade may actively contribute to achieving selected Sustainable Development Goals, through acting on key points of intervention, hence leverage points (Chan et al., 2020). Second, our objective was to show that (and how) we have implemented and understood our multi-methods and multi-level (macro/ meso/ micro) approach in the context of both causal and teleological explanations of system change related to agricultural trade and human agency. As Fisher et al. (2019: 115) highlight, a leverage points perspective can bridge causal and teleological explanations of system change, that is, change is seen to arise from variables influencing one another, but also from how human intent shapes the trajectory of a system. Furthermore, a leverage points perspective enables the examination of interactions between shallow and deep system changes (Fisher et al., 2019; Abson et al., 2017), the gradients of which we have attempted to bring alive from our 15 MATS case studies through identifying and prioritizing (also through a color code visible in the tables of the appendix) a number of deep levers for potentially significant realms of leverage arising from the thirty-one leverage points identified.

Such deep levers include focusing on strategic interventions in the social dimension to transform agricultural trade. We have shown how acting on the six social leverage points identified in MATS could trigger systemic changes in the agricultural trade that promise to enhance their positive impacts on several Sustainable Development Goals. A significant number of MATS case studies recognize the strategic role of collaboration, integration, and synergy among value-chain actors, and call for equitable, fair, and empowering approaches that strengthen the agency of stakeholders (esp. small-scale farmers and women) who are frequently marginalized from decision-making processes.

If the leverage points presented and discussed above were acted upon, in line with the prioritization suggested, significant progress could be expected on several SDGs pertaining to agricultural trade. In particular, we could expect to advance on poverty reduction (SDG 1), zero hunger (SDG 2), gender equality (SDG 5), decent work and economic growth (SDG 8), industry, innovation and infrastructure (SDG 9), reducing inequalities (SDG 10), responsible consumption and production (SDG 12) and partnerships for the goals (SDG 17).

Given its central importance, we return to one leverage point that has been emerging with striking frequency from the above work, namely the control and agency of stakeholders (especially small-scale farmers and women) who are frequently found marginalized from decision-making processes, hence the leverage point relating to the need to *reduce inequalities* (SDG 10). This finding is noteworthy for three reasons. First, most of the leverage points identified within MATS are envisaged to contribute to reduce inequalities - in the four dimensions presented above (13/15 in policy, 1/1 in human, 4/6 in social, 9/9 in economy and markets).

Second, IPBES evidence has highlighted *reducing inequalities* – naturally beyond the agri-food trade context - as a key leverage point, noting that “*Reducing inequalities is central to many sustainable pathways. Inequality often reflects excessive control and/or use of resources or power by one or more sectors of society at the expense of others. As societies develop and aim to ‘catch up’ in economic growth, inequality often emerges through control and distribution of unequal shares of finite resources and appropriation of ‘inexpensive’ labour through reduction in resource access.*” (Chau et al., 2020: 701). Through MATS we have therefore contextualized and specified this IPBES-central generic leverage point. Moreover, it seems that our MATS multi-actor and process-based evidence highlights that the key role of reducing inequalities corroborates with the same outcome of the iterative expert deliberation process that complemented the extensive review of scenarios and pathways to sustainability as part of the IPBES Global Assessment (Chau et al., 2020).

Third, we could consider a higher-level systemic implication of our finding, going even beyond the food systems nature considered above, keeping in mind the broad geographical and commodity scope of the MATS case studies robustly supporting this key finding of *reducing inequalities* as a key leverage point: recall previous evidence showing how reduced inequality can act to support the very effectiveness of those public authorities (governments) who are in charge of the capacity to collect taxes, regulate national trade policy instruments and environmental standards. In particular, a large body of previous work on economic development suggests that the very capacity of governments to function in their essential roles to collect taxes and implementing functioning legal institutions and corresponding policies can be

positively impacted by reducing inequalities (Acemoglu et al., 2015; Besley & Persson, 2014; Easterly, 2007; Wang, Madsen & Steiner, 2017).

Furthermore, our above discussion of thirty-one leverage points also provides evidence - through case study-specific conditions supporting actions for change - that it is important to recognize *interactions* across leverage points for deeper system changes in attempts to making agricultural trade more sustainable. Fischer et al. (2019) highlight the importance of acknowledging interactions between leverage points since there can be 'chains of leverage' whereby one type of change in a system precipitates another.

What does this point regarding 'chains of leverage' mean more specifically in the case of the MATS case studies? For example, although many MATS case studies focused on improving competitiveness of small-scale farmers, they identified at the same time the need to improve food self-sufficiency and the need to address socially undesirable impacts that come along with a strong focus on exports. Thus, the diversity of value-chain actors also in terms of small- and large-scale, the balance between focus on local self-sufficiency and export-driven competitiveness, and the need to address power imbalances that may result from export focus, as certain groups are strengthened in their privileged positions while other are marginalized, are emerging 'chains of levers' that require policymakers to jointly act on these leverage points.

Furthermore, we identified a striking corroborative finding on our 15 MATS agri-food case study results relative to the broader IPBES Global Assessment on the most important elements of pathways to sustainability (Chau et al., 2020), which suggests robustness in the identification of potential transformation pathways toward more sustainable agricultural trade. In particular, Chau et al. (2020) have identified eight leverage points: "(1)

Visions of a good life, (2) Total consumption and waste, (3) Latent values of responsibility, (4) Inequalities, (5) Justice and inclusion in conservation, (6) Externalities from trade and other telecouplings, (7) Responsible technology, innovation and investment, and (8) Education and knowledge generation and sharing". They also identified "five intertwined levers that can be applied across the eight leverage points and more broadly. These include: (A) Incentives and capacity building, (B) Coordination across sectors and jurisdictions, (C) Pre-emptive action, (D) Adaptive decision-making and (E) Environmental law and implementation". Not only do we see support from the MATS case studies on all eight leverage points above, but also on several of the *intertwined levers*, in particular on (A) incentives and capacity building (consider farmer education, skills, reduced child labor), (B) coordination across value chain levels up to national and international regulators, (C) pre-emptive action, especially at farmer levels with regard to risk management and value-chain resilience, not only sustainability practice adoption for climate change adaptation (D), and the need to provide incentives especially for small-scale farmers to reduce transaction costs of sustainability certification and standards adoption as well as implementation, as part of implementing national and supra-national environmental laws (E).

Through the above delineation of leverage points, their inter-relationships and their relationships with selected SDGs, we hope to have contributed further toward identifying deeper leverage points that are under-researched yet have greater potential for contributing toward systemic change (Fischer et al., 2019: 117). To emphasize, what are these deeper leverage points? Fischer et al. (2019) identify, among others, two such deeper leverage points related to *design*, namely information flows and self-organization, and two related to *intent*, namely changing mind-sets and changing paradigms, as four deeper

leverage points to be further explored in future works. In conclusion, when we consider our evidence from sections 2.1. to 2.4., above, we could argue that MATS case studies have contributed partially to each of the four deeper leverage points. First, regarding *information flows*, our MATS case studies give evidence through social leverage points (Table 4, Appendix) that the strengthening of associational activity of smallholder farmers to improve their participation in decision-making processes and their access to markets with better prices could be achieved through supporting the creation of effective cooperatives. Furthermore *information flows* could also be considered part of a 'chain of levers' as these are related to leverage point EM2 "Information access and transparency" (Table 5, Appendix), to PG4 "Policy coherence" (Table 2 PG4.2, Appendix), PG5 "Political leadership" (Table 2), and also to H1 "Knowledge and skills (Table 3 H1.1).

Second, regarding *self-organization*, we also provide extensive evidence from our case studies (coffee, poultry, cassava, banana, goats, cocoa, potato, olive oil, soy, dairy; Sub-Saharan Africa, Northern Africa, Latin America) on the role of social leverage points (Table 4, Appendix), as in many cases value chain actors work in isolation and fail to recognize the cumulated impact of their independence and interaction. So, incentivizing actors to integrate along the value chain can foster collaboration, a shared vision, common principles, and coordinated efforts to effectively address sustainability challenges.

Third, regarding *changing mind-sets* in the context of policy, governance and regulation (Table 2) we have provided evidence from the Cocoa value chains that promoting "no child labor" to foster a more sustainable and equitable future for children in Africa starts in the minds of the local farmers and value chains, not only with a European consumers' awareness and consciousness. More specifically, as part of CS 6 Cocoa in Ghana and Côte d'Ivoire, we have

specifically identified corporate responsibility for human rights violations to be promoted in consumer countries, 'Changing mindsets of consumers and companies to conduct due diligence along their value chain and increase awareness about human rights violations and take preventive measures'. Furthermore, as part of CS8 Sugarcane ethanol Perú and Brazil, we have identified due diligence processes within development banks that would require changing mindsets to promote assessments of socioeconomic and environmental risks before approving the loans for biofuel projects. And specifically arising from CS4 and CS9 in Sub-Saharan African countries (coffee, cassava, banana, goats, and cocoa), we also find evidence for the role of changing mindsets linked to land tenure and ownership rights: issues identified there relate to the mainstream mindset around gender and land, especially in regard to issues related with women's land tenure. The change on laws and property rights needs to happen together with a profound work on shifting mindsets, providing further evidence for a 'chain of levers'.

And fourth, regarding *changing paradigms*, we have also through MATS case studies provided evidence that acting on leverage points entails colliding paradigms and trade-offs (Mausch, Hall & Hambloch, 2020), not least among SDGs and reflected in food security vs. environmental sustainability or competitiveness targets, for example. Furthermore, we have also provided MATS evidence that questions the very underlying international food trade paradigm itself in the face of increasing geopolitization of food (Hosseini, et al., 2024). Important in this context is to recall that resilience and sustainability are intertwined notions in the transformability thinking (Folke et al., 2010), and that our MATS case studies provide both support and a call for more work on locally and socially embedded food systems (Sato et al., 2024), in order to advance

our ability to more radically change paradigms. Finally, the conclusions derived above come with several caveats. The limitations range from the methods limitations to the geographical limitations (neither India nor China, for example, were part of the MATS investigation) to the commodities coverage limitations, to the actors and researcher biases that have been acknowledged in more detail in earlier MATS Deliverables. Still, we hope that we have partially succeeded with devising transferable lessons and actionable leverage points, thereby advancing the sustainability debate on agricultural trade through increasing transparency and knowledge on the matter without losing sight of what matters most: the people and actors as they are individually affected, and the policymakers seeking actionable information.

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Appendix

TABLE 2. POLICY, GOVERNANCE, AND REGULATORY LEVERAGE POINTS AND POTENTIAL ACTIONS FOR TRANSFORMING THE AGRICULTURAL TRADE SYSTEM.

Policy, governance, and regulations dimension		
Leverage point	Potential actions for change	CS-specific conditions supporting actions for change
PG1. Agency in decision-making	PG1.1. Enhance stakeholder participation in policy design to clarify implementation frameworks and ensure inclusive decision-making.	<p>CS1a: Coffee (Uganda) Enhancing stakeholder participation in policy development can avoid misunderstandings and unrest among value chain actors, which can hinder the implementation of policy frameworks such as the Agricultural Sector Strategic Plan (ASSP).</p>
		<p>CS6: Cocoa (Ghana and Côte d'Ivoire) Enhancing stakeholder participation in policy development can avoid misunderstandings and unrest among value chain actors (including farmers and NGOs), which can hinder the implementation of policy frameworks such as Living Income Differential (LID).</p>
		<p>CS8: Sugarcane ethanol used as biofuel (Peru and Brazil) Improving stakeholder participation in policy design can effectively address disputes from land negotiations and governance issues fairly and transparently. This involves providing access to information and actively involving communities in decision-making.</p>
		<p>CS12: Bulk wine and bottle/package wine (South Africa) Engaging stakeholders along the value chain can ensure the active participation of local communities, previously disadvantaged individuals, wine farmers, government agencies, NGOs, and other relevant parties in decision-making processes. This approach incorporates diverse needs and perspectives, fosters strong community engagement, builds trust, and ensures initiatives are relevant and beneficial to the local population.</p>

PG2. Governance structures and mechanisms	PG2.1. Enhance governance structures to change the dynamics of agrifood systems and contribute to sustainable development.	CS1a: Coffee (Uganda) Improving the governance structure can help diminish the dominance of intermediaries as the primary market channel for coffee sales in Eastern and Central Uganda, potentially leading to significant changes in the coffee market dynamics and increasing farmers' incomes.
		CS1b: Coffee (Tanzania) Enhancing governance structures is essential for the coffee sector's long-term sustainability and poverty reduction. This approach supports the establishment of initiatives such as the coffee industry stabilization fund, a coffee research institute, free coffee seedling production and distribution, the promotion of cooperative institutions, public-private partnerships, and the creation of political will for the development of the coffee industry.
		CS4: Cassava, banana, goats and cocoa (Tanzania, Uganda, Ethiopia, and Ghana) Promoting the establishment of public agencies dedicated to export promotion can significantly enhance efforts to support the development of the cassava, plantain, and goat value chains, leading to increased export opportunities and economic growth. These agencies can assist stakeholders in developing and promoting their brands in target export markets while fostering Public-Private Partnerships to ensure comprehensive and effective support across the value chains.
	PG2.2. Enhance due diligence and accountability mechanisms to ensure projects and regulations account for	CS6: Cocoa (Ghana and Côte d'Ivoire) Lack of regulation leads to a race to the bottom regarding taking corporate responsibility for human rights violations in the value chain. Therefore, binding regulations must be promoted in consumer countries that oblige companies to conduct comprehensive human rights due diligence along their value chains. This includes risk assessment, implementation of preventive measures, and remediation when violations occur.

	<p>socioeconomic and environmental risks and impacts.</p>	<p>CS8: Sugarcane ethanol used as biofuel (Peru and Brazil) Improving due diligence processes within development banks can ensure that loans for bio-fuel projects undergo comprehensive assessments of socioeconomic and environmental risks. This involves conducting thorough impact assessments and actively engaging with local communities throughout the project evaluation process.</p>
		<p>CS14: Soy, part of the soy-meat complex (Brazil) Enhancing transparency and accountability mechanisms can ensure that all information related to the Authorization of Native Vegetation Conversion is publicly accessible, including applications, approvals, and associated documents. This involves establishing clear lines of accountability within regulatory bodies specifying roles and responsibilities for each authorization process stage. Furthermore, mechanisms should be established for the public and civil society organizations to report suspected illegal deforestation activities, ensuring these reports are taken seriously and investigated promptly.</p>
	<p>PG2.3. Promote remedy mechanisms to ensure justice, compensation, and support for rebuilding livelihoods.</p>	<p>CS8: Sugarcane ethanol used as biofuel (Peru and Brazil) Promoting remedy mechanisms can ensure communities receive justice, compensation, and the necessary support to rebuild and improve their livelihoods. This includes providing ongoing medical support and rehabilitation services to those affected by chemical exposure and environmental degradation and implementing environmental remediation projects to restore polluted water sources, soil, and ecosystems.</p>
	<p>PG2.4. Integrate social sustainability standards into organizational change to ensure companies address and prioritize social sustainability.</p>	<p>CS2: Oats and processed oats products (Finland, Sweden, and Germany) Reshape how companies approach and prioritize social sustainability to transition towards sustainability in the oats value chain by expanding involvement beyond dedicated sustainability units to include HR departments and the broader organizational structure.</p>

<p>PG3. Political crisis and corruption</p>	<p>PG3.1. Strengthen anti-corruption regulations to ban corporate bribery and undue benefits to political leaders.</p>	<p>CS8: Sugarcane ethanol used as biofuel (Peru and Brazil) Companies often promise unique benefits to political leaders and their communities, using this leverage to pressure them into requalifying land at a lower price or obtaining additional water extraction permits. To counteract such practices, it is crucial to enforce anti-corruption policies that prohibit companies from engaging in bribery or offering undue benefits to political figures.</p> <p>CS14: Soy, part of the soy-meat complex (Brazil) Local leaders in Brazil report corrupting authorities like notaries and judges to validate fake land titles. Strengthening anti-corruption regulations can enhance the enforcement of laws designed to prevent corruption, including imposing strict penalties on companies, political leaders, notaries, and judges involved in unethical practices. Additionally, it is essential to establish monitoring mechanisms to track corporate and governmental activities related to land use and resource extraction.</p>
<p>PG4. Policy coherence</p>	<p>PG4.1. Adjust international regulations to cope with the particularities of food system challenges in different regions.</p>	<p>CS7: Dairy products (West Africa) Promoting adjustments to policy regulations at the WTO and EPA levels can address the unique challenges West African nations face in safeguarding their dairy systems by ensuring transparency and accountability in implementing trade policies to build stakeholder trust.</p> <p>CS14: Soy, part of the soy-meat complex (Brazil) Promoting the refinement of the definition of savanna landscapes within EU regulations can involve broadening definitions and advocating for the inclusion of “other wooded land” and “natural grasslands” within the criteria for deforestation-free products (EUDR). This approach ensures comprehensive protection of savanna landscapes such as the Cerrado, underlining their importance for biodiversity conservation, water regulation, and ecosystem services.</p>

	<p>PG4.2. Strengthen coordination mechanisms between public agencies for greater cohesiveness, coherence, integration, and effectiveness.</p>	<p>CS5: Poultry meat (Ghana) Strengthening coordination mechanisms within ministries and agencies can help them work more cohesively, ensuring that policies are coherent, effectively implemented, and capable of driving sustainable agricultural development. This involves outlining clear roles, responsibilities, and collaborative strategies to ensure all policies are complementary and not contradictory.</p>
	<p>PG4.3. Simplify bureaucratic procedures to enhance farmers' active participation and engagement in food systems.</p>	<p>CS7: Dairy products (West Africa) Infrastructure investment can be crucial for upgrading milk collection centers, processing plants, and storage facilities. This effort necessitates the establishment of coordination mechanisms between government agencies, industry stakeholders, and development partners to effectively integrate policy measures into the broader framework of the ECOWAS initiative.</p> <p>CS1a: Coffee (Uganda) Simplified bureaucratic procedures can enable farmers to readily access and register for a wide array of services, resources, or opportunities, thereby enhancing their active participation and engagement in agricultural activities.</p>

<p>PG5. Political leadership</p>	<p>PG5.1. Improve the dissemination and outreach of government initiatives to engage and benefit to a broader spectrum of stakeholders.</p>	<p>CS5: Poultry meat (Ghana) Enhancing the dissemination of government initiatives can boost awareness and participation in poultry sector programs, ensuring they reach and benefit a broader spectrum of stakeholders across the entire value chain. This involves engaging with poultry farmers, associations, cooperatives, and other stakeholders at the grassroots level to communicate information about government programs effectively.</p>
<p>PG6. Power relations/ imbalances</p>	<p>PG6.1. Promote policies to prevent monopolistic practices.</p>	<p>CS15a: Potato (Egypt) Promoting policies to prevent monopolistic practices can address the issue of concentrated ownership of storage space contributing to higher urban potato prices, promoting fair competition, reducing costs, and improving market access for small-scale farmers and consumers alike.</p>
		<p>CS15b: Olive oil, crude form (Tunisia) Promoting regulations to address monopolies and speculation involves strengthening anti-trust laws and fostering competition to ensure fair market access and pricing.</p>
<p>PG7. Energy policies</p>	<p>PG7.1. Nuance of EU bio-fuel production policies to prioritize sustainable production in producer countries.</p>	<p>CS8: Sugarcane ethanol used as biofuel (Peru and Brazil) Nuancing biofuel production policies can advocate for policy reforms at the EU level. These reforms should aim to revise biofuel mandates and incentives, monitor mechanisms, and prioritize sustainable production methods in producer countries. This includes minimizing environmental and social impacts by addressing issues such as land rights, labor rights, and conservation practices.</p>
<p>PG8. Environmental regulations</p>	<p>PG8.1. Enhance environmental regulations to prevent deforestation, land degradation, and GHG emissions.</p>	<p>CS3: Dairy products (Finland) Nuancing regulations on manure application per hectare and greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions can unlock opportunities for herd expansion and agricultural productivity within environmental sustainability constraints. Adopting sustainable farming practices that minimize the environmental impact of dairy production is crucial.</p>

		<p>CS6: Cocoa (Ghana and Côte d'Ivoire) Enhancing environmental regulations can enforce laws that prevent deforestation and land degradation in cocoa-producing areas by developing robust monitoring and enforcement mechanisms to ensure compliance with sustainable practices and penalize illegal activities.</p>
PG9. Food policies	<p>PG9.1. Nuance international policies and design national provisions to enhance agricultural sovereignty.</p>	<p>CS15a: Potato (Egypt) Nuancing restrictive seed policies of the UPOV Convention can strengthen Egyptian agricultural sovereignty, support local farmers, and promote sustainable farming practices. Such measures could be complemented with provisions that allow smallholder farmers to save seed for non-commercial use and by increasing funding and support for national breeding programs focused on developing varieties adapted to local conditions.</p>
	<p>PG9.2. Encourage policies that advocate for including local agrifood products in national Food and Nutrition Security strategies.</p>	<p>CS4: Cassava, banana, goats and cocoa (Tanzania, Uganda, Ethiopia, and Ghana) Developing a specific policy statement can encourage the enhancement of the role of goat products (goat meat and goat milk) in Ethiopia's food and nutrition security strategy. This can be achieved by engaging with policymakers, agricultural stakeholders, and nutrition experts to advocate for their inclusion and highlight their nutritional benefits and economic potential.</p>
	<p>PG9.3. Promote price premiums to boost compliance and product quality.</p>	<p>CS12: Bulk wine and bottle/package wine (South Africa) Promoting price premiums can incentivize producers to invest in compliance measures, enhancing the overall quality of their wine. By endorsing wine exports that adhere to specific quality, sustainability, or social responsibility standards, these premiums help offset compliance costs, making it financially viable for producers to prioritize quality and sustainability initiatives. Price premiums also encourage continuous improvement in production practices and enhance profit margins and competitiveness in the international market.</p>

	<p>PG9.4. Support policies that promote sustainable agricultural practices to improve competitiveness.</p>	<p>CS5: Poultry meat (Ghana) Supporting policies that promote sustainable agricultural practices in Ghana can enhance the competitiveness and diversification of the agricultural sector, thereby contributing to economic development while safeguarding environmental and social standards. Such policies entail incorporating sustainability criteria into trade policies and industrial transformation agendas.</p>
		<p>CS11: Avocado and mango (Kenya) Supporting policies promoting good practices can ensure that certification standards explicitly require adopting sustainable farming techniques, animal welfare standards, and environmental conservation. Promoting good practices involves implementing regular audits and inspections to ensure certified farms consistently adhere to them.</p>
		<p>CS15a: Potato (Egypt) Nuancing agricultural and food policies can facilitate a transition towards a more comprehensive, sustainable, and self-reliant agricultural system. This approach reduces dependence on imported inputs and large agricultural companies, fostering a resilient and equitable agricultural sector.</p>
	<p>PG9.5. Enhance financial and technical support for farmers to meet sector requirements and adopt sustainable practices.</p>	<p>CS1a: Coffee (Uganda) Implementing the Agricultural Sector Strategic Plan (ASSP) has stirred unease among value chain actors, impeding its progress, mainly due to perceived high commercial levies such as coffee year subscription fees. In light of this, it is crucial to offer financial and technical support to assist farmers in meeting the requirements of the ASSP without feeling burdened by costs.</p>
		<p>CS5: Poultry meat (Ghana) Promote financial incentives or grants to poultry farmers to adopt renewable energy technologies and promote energy-efficient practices in their operations, aiming to reduce electricity consumption and alleviate the burden of high production costs.</p>

<p>PG10. Labor policies, regulations & legislations</p>	<p>PG10.1. Enforce labor regulations to comply with safety standards and protect workers' rights.</p>	<p>CS8: Sugarcane ethanol used as biofuel (Peru and Brazil) Enforcing labor regulations in producer countries can ensure compliance with safety standards and protection of workers' rights. Conducting rigorous inspections, imposing penalties for non-compliance, and implementing transparent pay structures and regular wage reviews are needed to enforce labor regulations.</p>
		<p>CS9: Coffee (Uganda) Farm workers are unable to collectively bargain, have less access to grievance mechanisms, and less leverage on their working conditions. Therefore, encouraging companies to adopt policies supporting workers' rights to collectively bargain and to develop and implement accessible, transparent, and effective workplace grievance mechanisms.</p>
		<p>CS11: Avocado and mango (Kenya) Enforcing labor regulations can ensure compliance with safety standards and the protection of workers' rights, including social services, insurance, and guaranteed medical care. This involves conducting rigorous inspections, imposing penalties for non-compliance, and implementing transparent pay structures with regular wage reviews.</p>
		<p>CS12: Bulk wine and bottle/packaged wine (South Africa) Enforcing labor regulations can ensure compliance with safety standards and the protection of workers' rights, including social services, insurance, and guaranteed medical care. This involves conducting rigorous inspections, imposing penalties for non-compliance, and implementing transparent pay structures with regular wage reviews. This will help to reduce the gap between VSS compliant and non-compliant wine farms.</p>
		<p>CS13: Dairy products (Algeria, Argentina, Brazil, France, Germany Italy, South Africa, USA, Zimbabwe) Enforcing labor regulations can ensure compliance with safety standards and the protection of workers' rights, including social services, insurance, and guaranteed medical care. This involves conducting rigorous inspections, imposing penalties for non-compliance, and implementing transparent pay structures with regular wage reviews.</p>

		<p>CS13: Dairy products (Algeria, Argentina, Brazil, France, Germany Italy, South Africa, USA, Zimbabwe) Promoting the implementation of minimum wage policies can ensure fair compensation for farm workers in Algeria and Zimbabwe, while strengthening legal protections to prevent exploitation and ensure fair treatment. More equitable pay structures can contribute to long-term sustainability and social stability in farming communities.</p> <p>CS13: Dairy products (Algeria, Argentina, Brazil, France, Germany Italy, South Africa, USA, Zimbabwe) Nuancing retirement age policies involves considering a gradual increase in retirement age to match rising life expectancies, thus safeguarding the sustainability of retirement systems. This entails implementing measures to alleviate poverty and enhance access to essential resources for older individuals, ensuring a dignified quality of life in retirement while also fostering opportunities for them to continue contributing as active and productive members of the workforce.</p>
	<p>PG10.2. Enhance policies that support fair labor practices and improve local community livelihoods to contribute to inclusive and sustainable agricultural growth.</p>	<p>CS5: Poultry meat (Ghana) Policies supporting fair labor practices and improving local community livelihoods contribute to inclusive and sustainable agricultural growth by prioritizing the needs and rights of various stakeholders, including local communities, smallholder farmers, marginalized groups, and poultry sector workers. Strategies should focus on promoting gender equality and youth participation in agriculture through targeted interventions, training programs, and capacity-building initiatives.</p>
	<p>PG10.3. Promote and enforce “no child labor” to foster a more sustainable and equitable future for children.</p>	<p>CS6: Cocoa (Ghana and Côte d'Ivoire) Promoting and enforcing “no child labor” in sustainability policies and standards can eradicate child labor and foster a more sustainable and equitable future for children. This involves conducting awareness campaigns on the harmful effects of child labor and the importance of education and child welfare, targeting both parents and the wider community, along with government initiatives that provide financial assistance or subsidies to farmers in times of low income, which helps alleviate the need for child labor to supplement family income.</p>

PG11. Land use policies	PG11.1. Nuance land policies to ensure local socioeconomic legislation supports ownership transformation.	CS12: Bulk wine and bottle/packaged wine (South Africa) Nuance land policies to ensure local socioeconomic legislation provides the essential support and flexibility to address challenges and adapt to evolving circumstances. This will facilitate meaningful ownership transformation and the inclusion of previously disadvantaged individuals while promoting sustainable development and ensuring compliance with socioeconomic standards.
	PG11.2. Strengthen land use regulations for enhanced sustainability, productivity, and resilience.	CS15b: Olive oil, crude form (Tunisia) Strengthening land use planning and management regulations can involve the development of comprehensive land use plans to identify suitable areas for olive cultivation and promote diversification of agricultural activities. By doing so, Tunisia can enhance its olive farming sector's sustainability, productivity, and resilience.
PG12. Legal framework on equity and non-discrimination	PG12.1. Promote gender-sensitive policies to prevent gender discrimination.	CS11: Avocado and mango (Kenya) Promoting gender-sensitive policies can establish and enforce measures that prevent discrimination based on gender in hiring, promotions, and salary decisions. Additionally, these policies should develop and implement strategies that foster an inclusive workplace culture where diversity is valued, and gender equality is prioritized.
	PG12.2. Strengthen legal frameworks to guarantee the protection of Indigenous territorial rights.	CS8: Sugarcane ethanol used as biofuel (Peru and Brazil) Strengthening legal frameworks can guarantee the enforcement of existing laws that protect Indigenous land rights and ensure mandatory and meaningful consultation with Indigenous communities on matters affecting their land and resources.
	PG12.3. Enhance enforcement mechanisms to ensure compliance with human rights laws.	CS9: Coffee (Uganda) Enhancing enforcement mechanisms can ensure compliance with national legislation safeguarding human rights, including equity and non-discrimination. This involves effective monitoring, investigation, and imposition of penalties for violations. Integrating human rights considerations alongside environmental and due diligence factors contributes to fostering responsible and sustainable business practices.

<p>PG13. Water policies</p>	<p>PG13.1. Enforce regulations for sustainable water management.</p>	<p>CS15b: Olive oil, crude form (Tunisia) Enforcing regulations for sustainable water management can promote sustainable agricultural practices, ensure water security, and safeguard the environment for future generations. This includes implementing restrictions on groundwater extraction and offering incentives for water-saving practices. Moreover, encouraging the adoption of water-efficient irrigation techniques, such as drip irrigation and micro-sprinklers, can significantly reduce water usage in olive oil production while maintaining crop productivity.</p>
<p>PG14. Official flows/ financial support to the agricultural sector</p>	<p>PG14.1. Promote investment in new infrastructure to strengthen the enforcement of regulations.</p>	<p>CS1a: Coffee (Uganda) The decentralization of inspection and certification processes should be considered to enhance the applicability of the Agricultural Sector Strategic Plan (ASSP) through investments in new infrastructure.</p>
<p>PG15. Social & environmental standards</p>	<p>PG15.1. Advocate for international social standards to advance gender equality and labor rights.</p>	<p>CS9: Coffee (Uganda) Promoting and enforcing “no child labor” in sustainability policies and standards can eradicate child labor and foster a more sustainable and equitable future for children. This involves conducting awareness campaigns on the harmful effects of child labor and the importance of education and child welfare, targeting both parents and the wider community, along with government initiatives that provide financial assistance or subsidies to farmers in times of low income or crop failure, which helps alleviate the need for child labor to supplement family income.</p>
		<p>CS12: Bulk wine and bottle/package wine (South Africa) Advocating for international policies on social standards can play a pivotal role in advancing gender equality and labor rights within the agricultural sector. By developing and enforcing labor regulations tailored to address gender disparities, such as ensuring equal pay for equal work and safeguarding against discrimination, we can foster inclusive growth in rural communities.</p>

	<p>PG15.2. Enhance trade measures tied to environmental and social performance to promote sustainable practices in food systems.</p>	<p>CS14: Soy, part of the soy-meat complex (Brazil) Enhancing trade measures tied to environmental and social performance can be crucial to promoting sustainable land use practices. It's imperative to advocate for stricter environmental and traceability requirements, especially to meet the demands of export markets, particularly China.</p>
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TABLE 3. HUMAN LEVERAGE POINTS AND POTENTIAL ACTIONS FOR TRANSFORMING THE AGRICULTURAL TRADE SYSTEM.

Human dimension		
Leverage points	Potential actions for change	CS-specific conditions supporting actions for change
H1. Knowledge & skills	H1.1. Enhance farmers' knowledge and skills to bolster their bargaining power and participation in decision-making.	<p>CS1b: Coffee (Tanzania) Enhancing farmers' knowledge and skills for accessing financial services can bolster their bargaining power, enabling them to negotiate better terms, secure essential financial services and inputs, and participate more effectively in decision-making processes. This, in turn, can significantly improve their position within the coffee value chain.</p>
		<p>CS15a: Potato (Egypt) Small-scale farmers frequently face challenges due to their limited bargaining power, often leaving them at the mercy of traders or intermediaries who control over prices and exert significant pressure on them to sell. Strengthening farmers' knowledge and skills is crucial as it empowers them to negotiate from a position of strength. This enhanced bargaining power enables farmers to secure better terms, devise effective marketing strategies, and establish fair contract farming arrangements. Engaging in transparent transactions with traders and intermediaries fosters fair trading practices, thereby reducing farmers' vulnerability to market exploitation.</p>

	<p>H1.2. Strengthen farmers' knowledge and skills to support sustainable production.</p>	<p>CS11: Avocado and mango (Kenya) Strengthening farmers' knowledge and skills is pivotal for promoting sustainable production practices and improving consumers acceptance of avocado and mango cultivation. Implementing targeted training programs on sustainable farming practices, environmental impacts, and cultivation techniques is essential. These efforts should be complemented by the development and dissemination of comprehensive resources such as guides, manuals, and online resources aimed at fostering best practices for environmentally sustainable agriculture.</p>
		<p>CS12: Bulk wine and bottle/package wine (South Africa) The wine sector requires comprehensive training and education for farm workers to foster sustainable production practices. Enhancing their knowledge and skills involves developing and implementing tailored training programs focused on agricultural techniques, business management, and financial literacy. These initiatives empower farm workers and contribute to the enhancement of working conditions.</p>

TABLE 4. SOCIAL LEVERAGE POINTS AND POTENTIAL ACTIONS FOR TRANSFORMING THE AGRICULTURAL TRADE SYSTEM.

Social dimension		
Leverage points	Potential actions for change	CS-specific conditions supporting actions for change
<p>S1. Collaboration, integration, and synergy among stakeholders</p>	<p>S1.1. Integrate stakeholders along the value chain to promote equity and fairness, improve competitiveness and safeguard livelihoods.</p>	<p>CS1a: Coffee (Uganda) Integrating stakeholders along the value chain can foster fair trade practices, diminish reliance on a small group of dominant players, and bolster initiatives that empower local farmers and aggregators to have a stronger voice and bargaining power within the coffee value chain.</p>
		<p>CS1b: Coffee (Tanzania) Most of the coffee value chain actors work in isolation and fail to recognize the cumulated impact of their independence and interaction. So, integrating stakeholders along the value chain can foster collaboration, a shared vision, common principles, and coordinated efforts to effectively address challenges. This approach helps achieve a competitive advantage of the coffee value chain.</p>
		<p>CS2: Oats and processed oats products (Finland, Sweden, and Germany) Processors and retailers wield significant influence due to their dominant position relative to farming and production capacity, impacting market prices in their favor during contract negotiations, to the detriment of producers. Integrating stakeholders along the value chain is vital for promoting equity and fairness in the agricultural supply chain. This implies to strengthen producer cooperatives and associations to negotiate collectively with processors and retailers enhances farmers' bargaining power, ensuring fairer contract terms, and thus improving economic viability for small farm operations.</p>

		<p>CS5: Poultry meat (Ghana) By integrating stakeholders throughout the value chain, smallholder farmers can enhance their bargaining power and market competitiveness. This entails establishing fair and transparent market mechanisms that ensure smallholder farmers have equitable access to essential resources such as feed, veterinary services, financing, and technology.</p>
		<p>CS7: Dairy products (West Africa) Equipping stakeholders with essential resources, knowledge, and alliances can counteract the influence of economic actors opposing changes in trade and tax policies that favor local milk production in the West African region. By engaging in evidence-based advocacy, fostering collaboration, and actively engaging with policymakers and regional institutions, stakeholders can effectively champion policy reforms that bolster the development of the local dairy sector, thereby contributing to sustainable economic growth and enhancing food security.</p>
		<p>CS9: Coffee (Uganda) Involving stakeholders across the coffee value chain promotes open and honest communication, building trust and transparency in decision-making. It enables collaborative identification and assessment of risks affecting all stakeholders, from climate-related challenges to market fluctuations and supply chain disruptions.</p>
		<p>CS14: Soy, part of the soy-meat complex (Brazil) Integrating stakeholders along the value chain can provide a collective voice by establishing institutions such as associations and grassroots organizations. These institutions can offer resources and bargaining power to poor family farmers, enabling them to negotiate more effectively with well-resourced and politically connected farmers.</p>
		<p>CS15a: Potato (Egypt) Engaging stakeholders along the value chain entails involving farmers from the outset of project planning and design to ensure their needs and livelihoods are considered. This collaborative approach fosters more successful and sustainable outcomes for both infrastructure projects and the agricultural communities they impact.</p>

	<p>S1.2. Encourage the establishment of alliances/ partnerships between food systems actors to foster collaboration and collectively address critical issues</p>	<p>CS4: Cassava, banana, goats and cocoa (Tanzania, Uganda, Ethiopia, and Ghana) Strengthening collaboration with non-state actors can effectively address various critical issues such as gender equality, pro-poor interventions, and climate change mitigation. Additionally, it can promote joint project investments between the government and the private sector.</p>
<p>CS4: Cassava, banana, goats and cocoa (Tanzania, Uganda, Ethiopia, and Ghana) Strengthening linkages between research, extension services, and farmers can enhance the adoption of best practices, helping value chain agents improve yields, increase cost efficiency, and meet quality standards for accessing national and international markets.</p>		
<p>CS6: Cocoa (Ghana and Côte d'Ivoire) Encouraging the establishment of cocoa producer alliances can facilitate coordination on crucial aspects such as supply management, demand projections, and price negotiations. This involves setting up channels for regular exchange of information and data among cocoa-producing countries, covering production forecasts, market trends, and consumption patterns. Additionally, harmonizing export policies, tariffs, and quotas is essential to prevent distortions in global cocoa markets and ensure fair competition among producers.</p>		
<p>CS15b: Olive oil, crude form (Tunisia) Promoting public-private partnerships can foster collaborative efforts to deliver cost-effective support services to smallholder farmers. Advocating for a reconsideration of government resource allocation ensures that support programs adequately address the needs of small-scale producers. This may entail providing subsidies or incentives to encourage private service providers to extend their reach to underserved communities.</p>		

	<p>S1.3. Strengthen associativity of smallholder farmers to improve their participation in decision-making processes and their access to markets with better prices.</p>	<p>CS1a: Coffee (Uganda) Strengthening associativity and promoting farmer group membership can enhance coffee quality, leading to higher incomes for farmers through increased prices.</p>
<p>CS1b: Coffee (Tanzania)With market liberalization of the coffee sector, the dominance of cooperative unions in the coffee sector waned, contrary to expectations.Strengthen associativity can improve market participation of smallholder farmers, increase farm incomes and reduce rural poverty, and ensure proper information flow amongst members in order to facilitate informed decision making.</p>		
<p>CS6: Cocoa (Ghana and Côte d'Ivoire) Strengthening associativity and promoting farmer group membership can cultivate an environment of inclusivity and mutual respect within cocoa cooperatives. This ensures that every member feels empowered to express their viewpoints and engage in collective decision-making processes. Additionally, this entails enhancing financial management practices within cocoa cooperatives to guarantee accurate budgeting, meticulous accounting, and transparent financial operations.</p>		

<p>S2. Gender equality</p>	<p>S2.1. Enhance women’s participation, ownership, and representation in decisions to advance gender equality and women’s empowerment in food systems.</p>	<p>CS2: Oats and processed oats products (Finland, Sweden, and Germany) Women’s representation in decisions regarding the purchase, sale, or transfer of assets is currently low. Enhancing women’s representation in these processes is essential for advancing gender equality and empowering women. Encouraging and supporting women to advocate for increased participation in decision-making processes is crucial. Additionally, providing women with access to financial services such as credit, savings, and insurance can economically empower them, facilitating investments in agricultural assets and promoting sustainable livelihoods.</p> <p>CS9: Coffee (Uganda) Promoting women’s land ownership includes facilitating access to and control over land resources through land redistribution and titling programs. This entails advocating for equal land ownership rights for women, including reforms in inheritance and property registration laws that recognize and safeguard women’s land rights. Additionally, fostering women’s participation in coffee sales is crucial for their economic and social empowerment within coffee-growing communities.</p>
<p>S3. Knowledge dynamics & capacity building</p>	<p>S3.1. Enhance extension services to support sustainable production, meet standards that improve livelihoods, and contribute to poverty alleviation.</p>	<p>CS1b: Coffee (Tanzania) Enhancing extension services can assist smallholder farmers in meeting standards that qualify for higher price premiums, increased incomes, and greater profits. This improvement not only improves livelihoods but also contributes significantly to poverty alleviation.</p>

		<p>CS3: Dairy products (Finland) Farmers’ understanding of the environmental and climate impacts of dairy production is crucial for promoting sustainable practices and gaining consumer acceptance. Enhancing farmers’ knowledge and skills supports sustainable production methods and improves the perception of dairy farming among consumers. Achieving this involves developing and offering training programs that focus on sustainable agricultural practices, environmental impacts, and precision farming techniques. Additionally, creating and disseminating comprehensive resources such as guides, manuals, and online courses covering best practices in environmentally sustainable dairy farming will further support these efforts.</p>
<p>S4. Research, innovation, and technology</p>	<p>S4.1. Promote funding for R&D to generate new knowledge and technologies.</p>	<p>CS1b: Coffee (Tanzania) Most Tanzanian coffee farmers struggle with low production rates due to the absence of improved varieties. Promoting funding for R&D can enhance coffee variety production, addressing challenges such as low yields, high pest control costs, poor quality, and fluctuating market prices. Developing high-yield, pest-resistant coffee varieties that adapt well to local conditions is critical.</p>
		<p>CS4: Cassava, banana, goats and cocoa (Tanzania, Uganda, Ethiopia, and Ghana) Research institutions have been responsible for developing and providing farmers with new varieties and breeds of crops (cassava, banana, and cocoa) and animals (goats) tailored to different consumer requirements. However, increasing funding for R&D is essential to develop the next generation of breeds and varieties capable of adapting to climate change and evolving consumer preferences.</p>
		<p>CS5: Poultry meat (Ghana) Promoting funding for R&D can generate new knowledge and technologies that advance the poultry industry. Providing training and education on modern farming practices, disease prevention, and business management empowers smallholder farmers to enhance productivity and resilience. This approach supports the development of comprehensive strategies and initiatives to address critical challenges and foster positive change in Ghana's poultry sector.</p>

		<p>CS11: Avocado and mango (Kenya) Increasing funding for R&D can prioritize innovative pest and disease management strategies and promote the adoption of new technologies and practices to boost overall crop productivity for mango and avocado cultivation. This will improve yields, reduce losses, and increase profitability for farmers, thereby fostering rural development and economic growth.</p>
	<p>S4.2. Enhance the documentation of good practices to contribute to sustainable and profitable farming operations.</p>	<p>CS4: Cassava, banana, goats and cocoa (Tanzania, Uganda, Ethiopia, and Ghana) Improving the documentation of best practices can significantly enhance goat production systems' productivity, health, and profitability, thereby promoting more sustainable and successful farming operations.</p>
<p>S5. Land tenure/ Ownership rights</p>	<p>S5.1. Promote women's land ownership to advance gender equality and contribute to the overall development of communities.</p>	<p>CS4: Cassava, banana, goats and cocoa (Tanzania, Uganda, Ethiopia, and Ghana) Promoting women's land ownership can enhance gender equality and improve access to financial products for women. Achieving this involves revising inheritance laws and property rights to eliminate gender discrimination. It also requires engaging community leaders and elders in discussions about the benefits of women owning land and how it can contribute to the community's economic development.</p> <p>CS9: Coffee (Uganda) Promoting women's land ownership involves facilitating access to and control over land resources through land redistribution and titling programs. This entails advocating for equal land ownership rights for women and reforms in inheritance and property registration laws to recognize and safeguard women's land rights. Additionally, fostering women's participation in coffee sales is crucial for their economic and social empowerment within coffee-growing communities.</p>

<p>S6. Societal awareness & measurement</p>	<p>S6.1. Shift the focus on food systems assessments to ensure the relevance and inclusivity of social aspects</p>	<p>CS2: Oats and processed oats products (Finland, Sweden, and Germany) Shifting the focus of food systems assessments to prioritize the inclusivity of social aspects within organizations can foster a balanced and holistic approach to data collection and reporting. This approach enables capturing both quantitative and qualitative dimensions of social impact, including factors such as workers' well-being, job satisfaction, and community engagement. Furthermore, it involves understanding stakeholders' perspectives and priorities regarding social impact to ensure relevance and inclusivity in assessments.</p>
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TABLE 5. ECONOMY AND MARKET LEVERAGE POINTS AND POTENTIAL ACTIONS FOR TRANSFORMING THE AGRICULTURAL TRADE SYSTEM.

Economy & market dimension		
Leverage points	Potential actions for change	CS-specific conditions supporting actions for change
EM1. Access to credits & funding	EM1.1. Promote alternative financing mechanisms to reduce compliance costs and enhance productivity in small-scale farms.	<p>CS4: Cassava, banana, goats and cocoa (Tanzania, Uganda, Ethiopia, and Ghana) Supporting the agricultural financial system can lead to more sustainable credit facilities and enhance the overall value chain of selected agri-food commodities. This can be achieved by creating financial products specifically designed for smallholder farmers and rural businesses and expanding the reach of financial services in rural areas through the establishment of more rural banks, microfinance institutions, and mobile banking options.</p>
		<p>CS12: Bulk wine and bottle/package wine (South Africa) Improving financial support for farmers can alleviate compliance costs. This assistance can manifest in diverse ways, including offering favorable loan terms to facilitate on-farm investments in social infrastructure and training programs.</p>
		<p>CS15b: Olive oil, crude form (Tunisia) Promoting alternative financing mechanisms for farmers can involve exploring options such as microfinance institutions, cooperatives, and community-based lending initiatives. These avenues can help fill the gap left by the withdrawal of government support, ultimately enhancing the resilience and productivity of small and medium-sized farms.</p>

EM2. Information access & transparency	EM2.1. Promote pricing transparency and traceability systems to ensure fair compensation for farmers.	CS9: Coffee (Uganda) Enhancing transparency and pricing mechanisms enables the tracking and documentation of coffee quality and pricing throughout the value chain, from farmers to middlemen and exporters. This fosters the adoption of transparent pricing practices, such as fair trade or direct trade, ensuring farmers receive equitable compensation for their produce.
		CS14: Soy, part of the soy-meat complex (Brazil) Promoting robust traceability systems can create immutable records of soy origin, ensuring transparency and traceability throughout the supply chain. This includes the use of blockchain technology and clear labeling and documentation to distinguish certified products from non-certified ones.
	EM2.2. Foster information symmetry and transparency for consistent and clear information disclosure in transactions.	CS1a: Coffee (Uganda) Fostering information transparency and digitization can maintain consistency and clarity in disclosing information across the coffee value chain. This allows consumers to access transparent details about sourcing practices, product attributes, coffee origins, production methods, and sustainability practices.
		CS1b: Coffee (Tanzania) Fostering symmetry and transparency of information ensures that all parties involved in a transaction have access to the same or similar information. By providing clear and accurate details about products, services, or transactions, smallholder farmers in the coffee value chain can fully benefit from fair trade programs.
		CS6: Cocoa (Ghana and Côte d'Ivoire) Fostering symmetry and transparency information by enforcing accountability in the cocoa sector through regular audits and inspections to monitor compliance with market regulations and protect the interests of all market participants. Involve a broad range of stakeholders, including cocoa farmers, civil society organizations, and industry representatives, in the decision-making process to ensure inclusivity and fairness.

		<p>CS8: Sugarcane ethanol used as biofuel (Peru and Brazil) Enhancing reporting requirements can ensure the enforcement of publicly disclosing relevant information about bioethanol supply chains, including sourcing practices, environmental impacts, and stakeholder engagement. This strengthens symmetry and governs transparency within the supply chain.</p>
<p>EM3. Public & private investments</p>	<p>EM3.1. Promote investments in modern infrastructure and technology to enhance agricultural productivity and sustainability.</p>	<p>CS4: Cassava, banana, goats and cocoa (Tanzania, Uganda, Ethiopia, and Ghana) Promoting investment in environmentally friendly technology (ridge-terracing to trap rainwater and drip irrigation for banana and cocoa, sub-soiling to retain more water per cassava plant, and paddock grazing of goats) can lead to significant improvements in water retention, soil health, and efficient land use, which are critical factors for enhancing productivity and sustainability in agriculture. By focusing on these practices, farmers can achieve better yields, more efficient resource utilization, and a more resilient farming system.</p>
		<p>CS5: Poultry meat (Ghana) Infrastructure for poultry and livestock production, processing and marketing remain a major challenge to the sector. Therefore, promoting investment in infrastructure development can facilitate the upgrading of processing facilities with modern equipment and technology. This not only enhances accessibility but also reduces transaction costs related to market access and transportation of feed and products.</p>
		<p>CS11: Avocado and mango (Kenya) Promote investment in upgrading storage facilities such as cold warehouses and transportation infrastructure like roads and refrigerated trucks, while expanding capacity to accommodate higher volumes of produce and alleviate congestion.</p>

		<p>CS15a: Potato (Egypt) Promoting investment in infrastructure development can garner government support and secure the necessary funding and resources to improve storage capacity for small farmers. This includes advocating for the inclusion of agricultural storage infrastructure in national and regional development plans and supporting the creation of agricultural innovation hubs that focus on developing and scaling affordable storage technologies.</p>
<p>EM4. Agricultural subsidies & trade tariff measures</p>	<p>EM4.1. Enhance state agricultural subsidies to support small and medium scale farmers be more sustainable and competitive.</p>	<p>CS10: Beef meat (Argentina, Brazil, France, Germany, Italy, Morocco, Namibia, South Africa, USA) Providing government grants and subsidies can facilitate access to capital specifically for technology adoption in the beef sector. This includes investing in infrastructure improvements to enhance the efficient movement and processing of beef products, making the industry more sustainable and competitive.</p>
		<p>CS5: Poultry meat (Ghana) By generating targeted financial instruments, policies can protect poultry farmers from price volatility by mitigating the rising costs of essential feed ingredients such as soybean meal, corn and fishmeal.</p>
		<p>CS12: Bulk wine and bottle/packaged wine (South Africa) Improving financial support for farmers can alleviate compliance costs. This assistance can manifest in diverse ways, including covering audit expenses through subsidies.</p>
		<p>CS13: Dairy products (Algeria, Argentina, Brazil, France, Germany Italy, South Africa, USA, Zimbabwe) Encouraging price support mechanisms can offer targeted subsidies to dairy farmers in regions where milk prices fail to cover production costs, thereby offsetting losses and ensuring farm viability. This involves ongoing monitoring of milk prices and production costs to pinpoint imbalances and implement corrective measures as necessary.</p>

		<p>CS15a: Potato (Egypt) Enhancing state subsidies can better support smallholder farmers by reintroducing targeted subsidies to provide financial relief and access to essential inputs such as fertilizers and seeds. Developing a tiered subsidy program that offers higher support levels for small and medium-sized farms compared to large commercial farms will ensure equitable resource distribution.</p>
	<p>EM4.2. Shift subsidies to performance-based models to contribute to sustainability.</p>	<p>CS3: Dairy products (Finland) Shifting subsidies to performance-based models can incentivize farmers to achieve specific outcomes related to sustainability, animal welfare, environmental stewardship, and ecosystem service preservation. This approach promotes efficiency improvements, encourages the adoption of more sustainable practices, supports farm consolidation and modernization efforts, and can foster local tourism opportunities, offering economic diversification.</p>
	<p>EM4.3. Enforce import restrictions policies and control measures to strengthen domestic production while fostering a shift toward sustainable food systems.</p>	<p>CS7: Dairy products (West Africa) Enforcing policies to ban or reduce palm oil imports can involve enacting legislation to ban the import of palm oil linked to deforestation. This can include a complete ban or targeted bans on palm oil from regions known for unsustainable practices. Additionally, setting strict quotas on the amount of palm oil that can be imported and gradually reducing these quotas over time can encourage a shift away from palm oil.</p>
		<p>CS7: Dairy products (West Africa) Gradually strengthening import restrictions can provide the local dairy sector with the necessary time to adapt to shifts in demand and production capacity. Making imports of milk powder contingent upon processors integrating a specific proportion of local milk into their production processes can effectively boost the demand for local milk and bolster support for domestic producers.</p>

		<p>CS10: Beef meat (Argentina, Brazil, France, Germany, Italy, Morocco, Namibia, South Africa, USA) Enhancing the implementation of tariffs and quotas on imported beef can make it less competitive compared to locally produced beef and limit the amount of beef that can be imported. This ensures a larger market share for local producers, helping to mitigate the negative impact of low-priced imports and strengthen the local beef production industry.</p>
EM5. Market access	EM5.1. Develop promotion and marketing strategies to strengthen the market access and visibility of agrifood products.	<p>CS1b: Coffee (Tanzania) Strengthening market access and visibility involves promoting Tanzanian coffee at international trade fairs, exhibitions, and coffee competitions to enhance its presence and reputation in global markets. Additionally, developing robust branding and marketing campaigns can effectively showcase the unique qualities and origin of Tanzanian coffee.</p>
EM6. Trade agreements and policy frameworks	EM6.1. Strengthen protective policies to shield farmers from volatile world market prices.	<p>CS1a: Coffee (Uganda) Uganda has entered into several bilateral and multilateral trade agreements, which have positively impacted coffee exports. However, to mitigate the risks associated with trade liberalization, Uganda needs to nuance its policies to protect farmers from volatile world market prices.</p>
		<p>CS1b: Coffee (Tanzania) Nuancing trade policies to safeguard both cooperative farmers and coffee quality, fostering a more conducive business environment for cooperatives and smallholder farmers. By ensuring that private coffee buyers operate fairly and transparently, policies would contribute to safeguard the interests of smallholder farmers.</p>
		<p>CS15b: Olive oil, crude form (Tunisia) Strengthening protective policies can diminish Tunisia's reliance on imported vegetable oils, bolster the surplus of exportable olive oil, and mitigate vulnerability to global market fluctuations. This entails negotiating favorable trade agreements to secure stable markets for olive oil exports and reliable sources for vegetable oil imports. Additionally, it involves developing policies that strike a balance between the export of olive oil and domestic consumption needs.</p>

	<p>EM6.2. Enhance domestic marketing policies for organized and competitive pricing.</p>	<p>CS4: Cassava, banana, goats and cocoa (Tanzania, Uganda, Ethiopia, and Ghana) Enhancing domestic marketing policies can lead to better-organized marketing systems, more efficient and competitive pricing. This can be achieved by developing and implementing consistent and transparent marketing policies that are regularly communicated to all stakeholders.</p>
<p>EM7. Competitive-ness</p>	<p>EM7.1. Implement practices that add value to agrifood products to ensure producing countries receive fair and equitable prices in both national and international markets.</p>	<p>CS6: Cocoa (Ghana and Côte d'Ivoire) Nuancing agricultural and food policies can promote local processing of cocoa and other commodities to capture more value along the supply chain and create additional employment opportunities. Additionally, advocating for fair trade practices and market access reforms is essential to ensure that producing countries receive fair and equitable prices for their commodities.</p> <p>CS15b: Olive oil, crude form (Tunisia) Promoting value-added olive oil products can drive the establishment of modern processing facilities in Tunisia, focused on refining crude olive oil into higher-value offerings such as extra virgin olive oil or diversified products like flavored oils and cosmetics, aimed at broadening revenue streams. Simultaneously, cultivating a strong brand identity for Tunisian olive oil in target markets becomes paramount, emphasizing its exceptional quality, authenticity, and distinctive flavor profiles.</p> <p>CS10: Beef meat (Argentina, Brazil, France, Germany, Italy, Morocco, Namibia, South Africa, USA) Encouraging the implementation of sustainability labelling for beef can attract consumer attention to sustainable products, influencing purchasing decisions and increasing access to international markets where sustainability is a key criterion. Additionally, it can enhance brand reputation and foster customer loyalty.</p>

<p>EM8. Voluntary standards</p>	<p>EM8.1. Promote Fair Trade accreditation to ensure sustainable production costs, fair wages, and good working conditions for farm workers.</p>	<p>CS1b: Coffee (Tanzania)Implementing fair trade standards for certified coffee production can offer smallholder farmers with higher prices that cover the average cost of sustainable agricultural production, access to financial services for agricultural investment, adoption of new technologies that are necessary for compliance with sustainability standards and protection against price fluctuations.</p>
		<p>CS11: Avocado and mango (Kenya) Strengthen fair trade standards for certified production can offer smallholder farmers with higher prices that cover the average cost of sustainable agricultural production, access to financial services for agricultural investment, adoption of new technologies that are necessary for compliance with sustainability standards and protection against price fluctuations.</p>
		<p>CS12: Bulk wine and bottle/package wine (South Africa) Promoting fair trade certification schemes can ensure farm workers receive fair wages and working conditions, encouraging consumers to support ethically produced agricultural products. Additionally, supporting living wage campaigns aims to establish wages enabling farm workers to meet basic needs like food, shelter, healthcare, and education.</p>
		<p>CS12: Bulk wine and bottle/package wine (South Africa) Promoting fair trade accreditation can ensure adherence to social standards valued by target niche markets, encompassing certifications related to fair labor practices, environmental sustainability, and community development. This effort involves crafting a compelling brand narrative around ethical sourcing, sustainability, and community engagement. Emphasizing the wine product's unique social and ethical attributes can set it apart from competitors. Additionally, maintaining transparency in the wine supply chain and production processes is crucial, providing consumers with clear information about the social standards adhered to and the impact of their purchasing decisions.</p>

	<p>EM8.2. Develop context-specific Fair-Trade standards to reflect local conditions.</p>	<p>CS1b: Coffee (Tanzania) Developing context-specific standards can help Fair Trade better reflect local conditions and realities in different regions. This involves recognizing and accommodating variations in production practices, environmental conditions, and socio-economic contexts. Additionally, creating mechanisms for transparent information exchange between producers and consumers—such as detailed labeling, storytelling, and digital platforms that provide insights into the production process and farmers' lives—can enhance understanding and support.</p>
	<p>EM8.3. Streamline compliance costs with regulations and certification standards to support farmers economically.</p>	<p>CS1b: Coffee (Tanzania) Streamlining the cost of compliance with regulations and certification standards can offer essential support and resources to assist farmers in meeting these requirements without facing excessive financial burdens. This approach ensures that certification standards contribute to the economic sustainability of farmers, rather than hindering their success.</p>
<p>EM9. Taxation in the agri-food value chain</p>	<p>EM9.1. Promote taxation incentives to reduce administrative burdens and bolster domestic products competitiveness in the market</p>	<p>CS1b: Coffee (Tanzania) Officials at the coffee estates reported having to pay multiple taxes at various stages of the coffee value chain. Streamlining transaction taxes can significantly alleviate financial pressure on the coffee estates, improving their profitability and sustainability. Consolidating these multiple taxes into a single, more manageable tax could simplify compliance and reduce administrative burdens.</p> <p>CS5: Poultry meat (Ghana) Help alleviate poultry producers' financial stress by promoting tax deductions or accelerated depreciation for investments in technology and expenses related to improving transportation logistics. And by developing strategies that directly address high feed-related costs (e.g., feed formulation optimization, exploration of feed alternatives, price negotiation, or vertical integration).</p>

		<p>CS11: Avocado and mango (Kenya) Promoting tax incentives, such as deductions or credits for investments in technology, infrastructure, and sustainable practices, can improve access to financing and encourage more investment in the sector. This also involves providing clear and consistent guidelines for businesses to follow, minimizing uncertainty and reducing the risk of incurring additional costs.</p>
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Strategic cross-cutting leverage points for achieving more sustainable agricultural trade: Insights from MATS case studies synthesis

MATS Deliverable 3.7 – Discussion paper (2)

MATS

making agricultural trade sustainable

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the European Union

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“MATS aims to identify key leverage points for changes in agricultural trade policy that foster the positive and reduce the negative impacts of trade on sustainable development and human rights. Particular attention is paid to SDG1 No Poverty, SDG2 Zero Hunger and SDG3 Good Health and Well-being, as well as SDG6 Clean Water, SDG13 Climate Action and SDG15 Life on Land.”

Summary

In Discussion paper 1 (DP1) we presented thirty-one leverage points that have the potential to contribute to more sustainable agricultural trade, arising from those actors, regions and commodities which were investigated as part of the MATS case studies (D3.5.). In this discussion paper, we focus only on those intervention points that we identify as *strategic cross-cutting* in their potential to transform the agricultural trade system. These are those leverage points recognized each in more than 5 of the 15 MATS case studies and located in at least two of the four SDG regions investigated under MATS [(1) Sub-Saharan Africa, (2) Northern Africa and Southern Asia, (3) Northern America and Europe, (4) Latin America and the Caribbean]. To arrive at these *strategic cross-cutting* leverage points, we started from the complete set of four sustainability dimensions [sections 2.1 to 2.4. in DP1, (2.1.) policies, governance, and regulations; (2.2.) economic and market variables; (2.3.) social structures and conditions; (2.4) knowledge and skills] and arrived here at the following three dimensions based on the above criteria for *strategic cross-cutting leverage points*: (2.1.) Policy, governance, and

regulations, (2.2.) Social dimension, and (2.3.) Economy and Markets. As a result, the identified *strategic cross-cutting leverage points* presented below are PG2 Governance structures and mechanisms, PG9 Food policies, PG10 Labor policies, S1 Collaboration, integration, and synergy among stakeholders, EM1 Access to credits and funding, EM3 Public and private investments, EM 4 Agricultural subsidies and trade tariff measures, and EM 6 Trade agreements and policy frameworks.

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“When transformative change takes off, the original incumbent way of doing things must decline – often in an accelerating way propelled by reinforcing feedbacks. There will be losers as well as winners. Hence it is vital to consider whether and how this exacerbates or reduces current inequalities”

Lenton et al. (2022: 12)

1. Introduction

In this discussion paper we focus on those intervention points that we identify as *strategic cross-cutting*, in terms of their capability to potentially transform the agricultural trade system. The objective is therefore to provide a further prioritization on intervention points relative to DP1, while utilizing the integrated modeling and multi-actor perspective of MATS. In this way, we extend the single-actor focus of previous work (e.g. Schulze et al., 2024). In fact, Schulze et al. (2024) identify this gap and call for such work, as they highlight that their “*present paper analyses the transition to sustainable food consumption, i.e., it focusses on behavior change at the consumer level. The paper should be understood as a starting point of a series of analyses. It should be complemented by a similar analysis for specific sub-groups of system actors, e.g., farmers, food companies, and retailers to better understand how the transition can be fostered and how (behavior) changes required from the different groups of actors are interconnected.*” (Schulze et al., 2024: 3).

In pursuing the above approach, we hope to make a small contribution toward an application of leverage-points-based thinking within a multi-level systems approach on governance issues (here: trade governance as part of the overall governance system) in a social–ecological context (Ostrom, 2007, Figure 1: a multitier framework for analyzing a social-ecological system). Applying a social–ecological systems lens, Chan et al. (2020: 694) identified eight priority points for intervention (leverage points) and five overarching strategic interventions (levers), which appear to be relevant to societal transformation. These eight leverage points are: (1) Visions of a good life, (2) Total consumption and waste, (3) Latent values of responsibility, (4)

Inequalities, (5) Justice and inclusion in conservation, (6) Externalities from trade and other telecouplings, (7) Responsible technology, innovation and investment, and (8) Education and knowledge generation and sharing. The five intertwined levers Chan et al. (2020) identified can, they suggest, be applied across the eight leverage points and more broadly. These eight include: (A) Incentives and capacity building, (B) Coordination across sectors and jurisdictions, (C) Pre-emptive action, (D) Adaptive decision-making and (E) Environmental law and implementation. Chan et al. (2020) further suggests that the levers and leverage points each enables others, likely leading to synergistic benefits, further highlighting the role of strategic leverage points. The following short discussion in this DP2 focuses on those intervention points that were identified as strategic to transform the agricultural trade system by a significant number and diversity of MATS case studies. Therefore, the focus here is on what we call *cross-cutting leverage points*, relating to three dimensions and associated leverage points, based on the above criteria for strategic cross-cutting leverage points: 2.1. Policy, governance, and regulations, 2.2. Social dimension, 2.3. Economy and Markets. Based on these dimensions, the *strategic cross-cutting* leverage points include PG2 Governance structures and mechanisms, PG9 Food policies, PG10 Labour policies, S1 Collaboration, integration, and synergy among stakeholders, EM1 Access to credits and funding, EM3 Public and private investments, EM 4 Agricultural subsidies and trade tariff measures, and EM 6 Trade agreements and policy frameworks.

2. Strategic cross-cutting leverage points toward more sustainable agricultural trade

Through our 15 MATS case studies – as they have been applied to different commodity, region and actor settings around global agri-food value chains – we aim to offer key insights into the *enabling conditions* for more sustainable trade.⁴ These *enabling conditions* we investigated in the various contexts of the agri-food systems (local and global agri-food value chains) and with regard to agricultural trade can be seen to interact with *interventions*, so as to potentially transform the agri-food system towards higher levels of sustainability (left and right boxes, Figure 1, below). These interactions could be understood through factors that drive *reinforcing feedback*, namely strategic cross-cutting leverage points and related interventions.⁵ As Figure 1 shows in its centre, we consider cross-cutting leverage points derived from four sustainability dimensions elaborated during sections 2.1 to 2.4. in DP1, namely (2.1.) *policies, governance, and regulations*; (2.2.) *economic and market variables*; (2.3.) *social structures and conditions*; (2.4) *knowledge and*

⁴ The term *enabling conditions* has been introduced in the context of discussing tipping points in social-technological-ecological systems (Lenton et al. (2022) and in other sustainability contexts by previous works (e.g. Cisneros-Montemayor et al., 2021; Kuyvenhoven, 2004).

⁵ *Reinforcing feedbacks* have been introduced mathematically and in different sustainability contexts before, highlighting that a system change can be expedited through the amplification of initial changes (Tàbara et al., 2013; Zeppini et al., 2014; Lenton et al., 2022; Schulze et al., 2024). They are to be distinguished from *policy feedbacks* which focus on the continuous interactions between public policy, societal outcomes, and how these outcomes affect policy actors in ways that influences politics and subsequent policymaking (Weible, 2014; Edmondson et al., 2019).

skills. From these four dimensions we have identified *strategic cross-cutting* leverage points associated with only three remaining sustainability dimensions, namely (i.) policy, governance, and regulations, (ii.) social dimension, and (iii.) economy and markets, which we consider as priority interventions (Chau et al., 2020). These cross-cutting leverage points are also considered strategic in MATS since they cut across different commodities, actors and regions, considering that such diversity is also considered as a measure of relevance for the potential transformation of the agricultural trade system.

Taking into account the IPBES (2019) report and Figure 2 from Chau et al. (2020: 699), we consider in our Figure 1 that these *strategic cross-cutting leverage points*⁶ are below the pivot of the lever which is held by the multiple actors investigated in the different MATS value chains (case studies). The lever can thus be thought applied at priority interventions (e.g. strengthen governance structures in global food value chains by ensuring accountability, due diligence and justice, together with enforcing labor policies that ensure safe and fair labor practices). In this conceptualization, our *strategic cross-cutting* leverage points are part of the amplification thinking underlying the reinforcing feedbacks: they are so central that if they get implemented and kick-started jointly, they will lead to accelerating our food system change toward making trade more sustainable, as reflected in the MATS-investigated SDGs displayed at the end of the lever in Figure 1.

⁶ PG2 Governance structures and mechanisms, PG9 Food policies, PG10 Labor policies, S1 Collaboration, integration, and synergy among stakeholders, EM1 Access to credits and funding, EM3 Public and private investments, EM 4 Agricultural subsidies and trade tariff measures, and EM 6 Trade agreements and policy frameworks.

FIGURE 6. ENABLING CONDITIONS, INTERVENTIONS AND REINFORCING FEEDBACKS IN AN INTEGRATED MODEL-BASED CONTEXT

When considering the second middle box in Figure 1, referring to “integrated model-based assessment”, reference is made to MATS D3.3. ([Report and Policy Brief on the results of the integrated model-based assessment](#)) because we consider that the *enabling conditions* which were identified through the case studies work connect to the interventions as part of our integrated model-based assessment, since this integrates systems thinking at multiple levels from a qualitative and quantitative perspective.⁷ For example, enabling conditions (competitiveness) were considered to derive recommendations for interventions (through Computable General Equilibrium modelling, the introduction of a Carbon Border Adjustment Mechanism (CBAM) was considered as a compensatory measure for reducing carbon leakage and competitiveness loss of energy-intensive EU industries). In particular, modelling was performed at different levels of stringency of interventions that assume a system which is adjusting to changing policy conditions (e.g. climate clubs in the case of CBAM), reflecting some feedback loops between the *interventions* (right hand side Figure 1) and changing and yet case-study specific *enabling conditions* (left hand side Figure 1).

⁷ D3.3 Report and policy brief on the results of the integrated model-based assessment, <https://zenodo.org/records/10559510>: Three modelling techniques are used, one qualitative and two quantitative (one applied at the national level, and one focused on international trade dynamics). The use of three modelling techniques is required to assess trade policy frameworks and instruments (drivers), in terms of shaping demand, determining production practices and generating social and environmental impacts (at global, national and local level), measured using various SDGs. On top of quantitative modelling (integrated systems models, spatial analyses, Cost Benefit Analysis), we applied qualitative modelling (i.e., system maps) using a participatory, co-creation approach for CS2 on oats (EU, Finland), CS3 on dairy (EU, Finland), CS5 on poultry (Ghana), CS10 on beef (EU, Africa, South America), CS13 on milk (EU, Africa, America), CS14 on pork (Brazil), CS15 on olive oil (Tunisia). This offers a wide variety of applications across sectors and geographies. Each system map, also called Causal Loop Diagram (CLD) is fully customized to the socio-economic and environmental context analysed and offers insights on the dynamic interrelations existing across indicators. This analysis offers information on the transformative potential of policy intervention for agricultural trade sustainability.

Furthermore, we highlight the connection to MATS D3.3. ([Report and Policy Brief on the results of the integrated model-based assessment](#)) since a system dynamics perspective was implemented (system maps in the form of causal loop diagrams, CLDs, as part of qualitative modelling) which reflects the underlying logic of Figure 1, in that when interventions are designed, it is expected that they transform a system because an intervention could either reinforce the changes triggered by acting on leverage points (reinforcing feedback loops) or could balance such changes in terms of counteracting them (balancing feedback). When we consider the example of the dairy sector here investigated in MATS, the CLD reflects how improving the competitiveness of this sector could lead policymakers to paying greater attention to that sector, therefore reinforcing the interventions that contribute to the sector's competitiveness. Or in the case of the Nordic oats value chains, increased attention to social and environmental sustainability (evidenced through stakeholder interviews and surveys) is expected to result in requests for fairer pricing vis-à-vis the farmers by consumers and government agencies.

To emphasize, the above MATS integrated-model-based representation of reinforcing feedback loops building on system dynamics thinking contributes in two ways. First, it enables us to apply the conceptual understanding of reinforcing feedbacks (Tàbara et al., 2013; Zeppini et al., 2014; Lenton et al., 2022) to the practical multi-actor setting of MATS, visible in the system dynamics implementation, providing practical insight to the conjecture that negative feedback loops can lead to maintain the current state of a system, whereas positive reinforcing feedback loops can accelerate system change if strong enough (e.g. Lenton et al., 2022; Schulze et al., 2024). Second, in our Figure 1, we are adapting Lenton et al. (2022) and the consumption-focused application of Schulze et al. (2024) to our broader multi-actor setting in MATS.

In particular, we have been inspired by Figure 1 of Schulze et al. (2024) and the underlying tipping-point conceptualization, which is itself adapted from Lenton et al. (2020). Figure 1 of Schulze et al. (2024) shows an interaction between enabling conditions (to move towards a tipping-point) and interventions (to trigger positive tipping of consumer behavior), connected in the middle by reinforcing feedbacks (to accelerate the shift from one state of the system to another). We are thus not only adapting this figure to the systems-thinking underling the system approach of the integrated modelling approach of MATS, but also to a broader multi-actor setting that could be applied to other multi-actor settings and research projects beyond MATS.

In the following discussion, we focus on those intervention points identified as *strategic cross-cutting* by a significant number and diversity of case studies, to potentially transform agricultural trade.

Using these criteria, the most relevant leverage points out of the initial four sustainability dimensions 2.1. to 2.4. presented in DP1, are the following three (2.1. to 2.3.) and their underlying strategic cross-cutting leverage points, associated country- and commodity context, and SDGs addressed:

2.1. Policy, governance, and regulations

2.1.1 Cross cutting leverage point in policy and governance to transform agricultural trade

- *Governance structures and mechanisms (PG2)*: This is supported by case studies working on eight agrifood products in ten different countries across Sub-Saharan Africa, South America, and Europe. These case studies highlight the need for accountability, due diligence, and justice mechanisms in governance and political structures that contemplate the social and environmental dimensions of trade besides the economic one.
- *Food policies (PG9)*: This is supported by case studies working on nine agri-food products in seven countries across Sub-Saharan Africa and

North Africa. These case studies highlight the need to nuance food policies to smallholder farmers' needs. In that sense, they call for enhancing agricultural sovereignty by introducing local products in national food security strategies, supporting farmers technically and financially to be more sustainable and competitive, and instilling price premiums for those to act more sustainable and produce better quality products.

- *Labor policies and legislations (PG10)*: This is supported by case studies working on seven agri-food products in 16 MATS countries across Sub-Saharan Africa, North Africa, North America and Europe, and South America. These case studies highlight the need to enforce labor policies that protect farmers and workers' rights and prohibit child labor, fostering a sustainable and equitable future for children and local communities.

2.2. Social dimension

2.2.1. Cross cutting leverage point in the social dimension to transform agricultural trade

- Collaboration, integration, and synergy among stakeholders (S1):* This is supported by 11 of the 16 agri-food commodities analyzed in MATS, in countries located in more than two SDG regions – Sub-Saharan Africa, Northern Africa & Western Asia, Latin America and the Caribbean, and Europe & Northern America. These case studies call for **equitable, fair, and empowering approaches** and strategic alliances that strengthen the **agency of stakeholders** who usually are marginalized from decision-making processes. Frequently the agency of stakeholders here relates to small-scale farmers and empowering women in MATS-investigated value chains (incl. coffee, poultry, dairy, potato). Yet self-empowerment and agency are also relevant for strengthening the functioning of cooperatives as well as to governance systems where common resource pools are central (deforestation). In particular, collaboration, cooperation and agency have been enduring themes related to self-organized monitoring, trust, reciprocity and enforcement, which have repeatedly played important roles in explaining successful efforts at collective action problems (Cárdenas et al, 2004; Ostrom, 2007). In light

of the EU's Regulation on deforestation-free supply chains (DEFOR), it could not only be expected that collaboration and integration of small-scale actors in global value chains is further impeded, as global value chain leads (buyers) will likely de-select these small-scale actors as a function of higher transaction costs of monitoring and enforcement.⁸ It could also be expected that self-organized monitoring, trust and reciprocity in those local value chains (social capital in those communities) are further weakened, reversing parts of the very sustainability objectives of the EU DEFOR policies themselves.

⁸ https://ec.europa.eu/commission/presscorner/detail/en/ip_22_7444

2.3. Economy and Markets

2.3.1. Cross cutting leverage point in the economy and market dimension to transform agricultural trade

- *Access to credits and funding (EM1)*: This is supported by six out of 16 agri-food products analyzed in MATS, in six different countries across Sub-Saharan Africa and Northern Africa. These case studies highlight the need for alternative financing mechanisms designed for smallholder farmers to enhance resilience and productivity.

- *Public and private investments (EM3)*: This is supported by eight out of 16 agri-food products analyzed in MATS, in six different countries across Sub-Saharan Africa and Northern Africa. These case studies call for investments in modern and environmentally friendly technology and infrastructure to enhance productivity, cost-efficiency, and sustainability.
- *Agricultural subsidies and trade tariff measures (EM4)*: This is supported only by five out of 16 agri-food commodities in all the SDG regions analyzed in MATS – Sub-Saharan Africa, Northern Africa and Western Asia, Latin America and the Caribbean, and Northern America and Europe. These case studies call for enhancing state agricultural subsidies to support small and medium-scale farmers to be more sustainable and competitive. For instance, subsidies that help them ensure farm viability by alleviating audits and standards compliance costs, mitigating the rising costs of essential inputs, or adopting technology that enhances their competitiveness. Concerning trade-tariff measures, case studies call for enforcing import restriction policies to protect local farmers and shield the domestic market from unsustainable practices.
- *Trade agreements and policy frameworks (EM6)*: This is supported by six out of 16 agri-food products analyzed in MATS, in five different countries across Sub-Saharan Africa and Northern Africa. These case studies call for protective policies to shield farmers from the risks of trade liberalization – e.g., volatility of world market prices, fairness and transparency in trade transactions, and food self-sufficiency.

3. Discussion and conclusions

Considering the large number of leverage points (thirty-one) we identified in MATS as a result of the multi-actor, commodity, and region analyses and as discussed in Discussion Paper (DP1), this discussion paper DP2 has attempted to provide a further prioritization for interested policymakers and value chain actors, by identifying those intervention points that could be viewed as *strategic* and *cross-cutting* in their ability to transform the agricultural trade system. This definition of *strategic cross-cutting* was based on those leverage points that were each recognized in more than 5 of the 15 agrifood products MATS case studies, and located in at least two of the four SDG regions covered by MATS. As a result, these cross-cutting leverage points relate to three dimensions based on the above criteria for *strategic cross-cutting* leverage points out of the original four dimensions (DP1): (i.) policy, governance, and regulations, (ii.) social dimension, and (iii.) economy and markets. Based on these three dimensions, the *strategic cross-cutting* leverage points identified include Governance structures and mechanisms, Food policies, Labour policies, Collaboration, integration, and synergy among stakeholders, Access to credits and funding, Public and private investments, Agricultural subsidies and trade tariff measures, and Trade agreements and policy frameworks. These were each contextualized above also in terms of the commodity and regional context they emerged from. Since these *strategic cross-cutting leverage points* are related to the leverage-points analysis and its literature in DP1, the interested academic reader is referred to DP1 for consulting additional academic literature which is detailed there. We also refer to DP1 those stakeholders who wish to deepen their understanding of the contextual conditions that provide to key points of intervention and their power to transform the system. Moreover, these *strategic cross-cutting* leverage points

are related to a set of contributing Sustainable Development Goals investigated under MATS. In this DP2, we have tried to conceptually show how these *strategic cross-cutting* leverage points can be seen in the bigger systems perspective. Building on previous works, we conceive interactions between *enabling conditions* to move us towards a desired higher sustainability level of agricultural trade and *interventions* that accelerate change, connected through *reinforcing feedbacks*. In this conceptualization, our *strategic cross-cutting* leverage points are part of the amplification thinking underlying the reinforcing feedbacks, and a key component for leveraging key points of intervention to move towards the desired transformation in agricultural trade. In other words, these strategic cross cutting leverage points are so central that if they get implemented and kick-started jointly, they have the potential to accelerating our food system change toward making trade more sustainable, as reflected in the MATS-investigated SDGs.

We hope that this discussion paper DP2 has not only simplified the challenges facing policymakers in looking for entry-points and prioritization, but that we have also contributed with a broader multi-actor application of the interplay of enabling conditions, reinforcing feedbacks and interventions to trigger systemic changes that could be applied to other research projects with multi-actor settings beyond MATS.

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